

Traces of the Riemann zeta function on the complex plane.

Author: Dante Servi ORCID: 0000-0002-8664-3415

Abstract.

Given for example the formulation $\zeta(s) = \sum_{n \geq 1} \frac{1}{n^s}$, at each increment of (n) a new point on the complex plane is defined. Starting from the origin of the complex plane, the 'traces' in question are formed of the vectors that connect (in sequence) these points.

Speaking of (s), I call (a) the real part and (b) the coefficient of the imaginary part, then $s=a+ib$.

Provided that (b) is sufficiently large, the traces resulting from the zeta function of Riemann can be divided into three parts, below I call the first two useful, for a reason that I will explain later.

The first useful part of the traces tends to move away from the origin, it develops in a convoluted way reaching variable distances.

The second useful part of the traces, is characterized by the presence of particular polygonal spirals that follow one another, always better formed. Seen the similarity with clothoids I called them "pseudo-clothoids".

The two useful parts behave like two arms of a mechanism that makes them both rotate, in case the value of (b) is changed in search of a zero. The second arm is the extension of the first, its rotation is in synchrony with that of the first arm, to which is added.

The rotation of the two arms cyclically brings the origin that concludes the second arm, to pass where the origin of the complex plane is located, but intercepts it only if the lengths of the two arms compensate.

In this manuscript I highlight that the Riemann hypothesis is true for the reason that, only if the real part of (s) is 1/2 it is possible to compensate the lengths, of the two useful parts of the trace.

The value of (b) is the engine of the rotations, only if $a=1/2$, the value of (b) results neutral with respect to the distances, between the two origins of the pseudo-clothoids.

Premise.

The third part of the trace is a spiral, which can be divergent or convergent.

The important fact is that the origin of the spiral in question coincides with the second and last origin of the pseudo-clothoid that precedes it.

In this manuscript I present three formulations, but I mainly analyze, the traces resulting from what I will call formulation (1) below.

The formulation (1), is distinguished from the other two, for not being convergent if $a=1/2$.

The divergence that occurs if $a=1/2$, is due to the spiral with which the trace ends.

All the spirals are formed only if $b \neq 0$, in this manuscript I consider that is $b > 0$.

I discovered that given a value of (s) in which $b > 0$, the origin of the last spiral of a trace resulting from the formulation (1), always coincides with the convergence point recognized resulting from the Riemann zeta function, for that given value of (s).

This manuscript therefore has two purposes, highlight that the Riemann hypothesis is true and furthermore highlight that the conditions exist, to accept the last origin of the trace, as a useful result of the zeta function.

I am not a mathematician, but thanks to PARI-GP and a two-dimensional CAD, I think I managed to discover why the Riemann hypothesis is true.

PARI-GP is a calculator known to mathematicians, with the CAD I had made mechanical drawings for over 20 years. Unfortunately the type of approach that I was able to use and the fact that I am not a mathematician, does not allow me to give a better exposition.

I have been very rigorous in carrying out the research, for this reason I am extremely convinced that what I state in this manuscript, is true and verifiable.

I hope the effort I put into describing how I was able to achieve the results is appreciated.

1. The Riemann Hypothesis.

In 1859 the great German mathematician Bernhard Riemann, in one of his manuscripts, he presented a new version of Euler's product. (The manuscript has been transcribed and translated, see link on the last page) The innovation introduced by Riemann, was to use for (s) the complex numbers. He further hypothesized that, all "non-obvious" zero of his version of the zeta function, are complex numbers with the real part $1/2$. Exist only one point that defines the "non-obvious" zero and this point is the origin of the complex plane. In this manuscript I consider only the "non-obvious" zero.

Contents

Premise	1
1. The Riemann Hypothesis.	2
2. The three formulations of the zeta function, which I studied.	3
3. Introduction.	3
4. For what reasons is Riemann hypothesis true, for the traces resulting from formulation (1).	8
5. The first tools I equipped myself with.	10
6. Graphic analysis of the traces resulting from the formulation (1).	10
6.1. Pseudo-clothoids and their origins.	11
6.2. Verification of the method of calculating the origins of pseudo-clothoids.	18
7. For what reason the orientations of the axes of the pseudo-clothoids, are symmetrical, to the orientations of the corresponding vectors, in the first part of the trace.	26
8. A function to calculate the (α) angle.	30
9. For what reason, if $a=1/2$, the value of (b) is neutral as regards the distance, between the two origins of the pseudo-clothoids.	31
10. Method to locate the origin of the last divergent polygonal spiral, belonging to a trace resulting from the formulation (1).	32
11. For what reasons is Riemann hypothesis true, for the traces resulting from formulation (3).	35
12. Graphic analysis of the traces resulting from the formulation (3).	36
12.1. Verification of the method of calculating the origins of pseudo-clothoids.	40
13. Consequences of part $(-1)^n$ on the traces of the Riemann zeta function, resulting from formulations (2) and (3).	44
14. Graphical analysis of the traces resulting from the Riemann's version, of the Euler's product.	46
Appendix A. Use of Computer Aided Design.	50
A.1. Characteristics that the CAD must have.	50
A.2. PARI-GP functions and commands, useful for obtaining the data needed by the CAD.	50
A.3. Checking and adapting text for CAD.	52
A.4. Data transfer to CAD.	52
Appendix B. False pseudo-clothoids.	54
Appendix C. Further evidence of symmetry and confirmation of the validity of functions (6), (7) and (8).	55
Appendix D. Two vectors to calculate the last origin (Of) more precisely.	56

2. The three formulations of the zeta function, which I studied.

$$\zeta(s) = \sum_{n \geq 1} \frac{1}{n^s} \quad (1)$$

$$(2^{1-s} - 1)\zeta(s) = \sum_{n \geq 1} (-1)^n \frac{1}{n^s} \quad (2)$$

$$\zeta(s) = \sum_{n \geq 1} (-1)^n \frac{1}{n^s} \quad (3)$$

- The formulation (1) simply does the summation of $1/n^s$, this is the second part of Euler's product, used by Riemann. The first vector of the trace always ends in $1 + 0i$.
- The formulation (2) seems to me that is considered "the classical formula" of the function zeta of Riemann. Note that the $(2^{1-s} - 1)$ part occurs after the summation is complete. The intervention of this part rotates and resizes the trace, resulting from the summation, based on the origin of the complex plane.
- I obtained the formulation (3) from the formulation (2) by removing the $(2^{1-s} - 1)$ part. In addition to formulation (1) only the part $(-1)^n$ remains.

By reversing the direction of the vector when (n) is odd, the part $(-1)^n$ makes convergence possible when $a > 0$. The first vector of the trace always ends in $-1 + 0i$.

It should be noted that, only when the point of convergence coincides with the origin of the complex plane, the result of this formulation is the same as that produced by formulation (2).

- Observations relating to formulation (2). Valid for $b \neq 0$.

There can be no doubt that it is the origin of the complex plane, the basis with respect to which, part $(2^{1-s} - 1)$ rotates and resizes the trace resulting from the summation, since it is from that point that the trace begins. For this reason, the zero of formulation (3) and formulation (2) coincide.

There can be no doubt that part $(2^{1-s} - 1)$, has no influence on Riemann hypothesis. For this reason, I do not thoroughly analyze the traces resulting from formulation (2).

It must be recognized that the $(2^{1-s} - 1)$ part present in the formulation (2), reports the convergence points of formulation (3), that do not coincide with the origin of the complex plane, to coincide given the same (s), with the origin of the divergent spiral, with which the traces resulting from formulation (1) concludes.

3. Introduction.

Despite their differences, the three formulations have one characteristic in common.

Provided that, $b > 0$, in the traces resulting on the complex plane from any of the three formulations, there is always at least one spiral with its origin. Being composed of vectors, they are polygonal spirals, which can be convergent or divergent.

Starting from $b \geq \pi$ for formulations (2) and (3), starting from $b \geq 2\pi$ for formulation (1), is observed more and more clearly as (b) grows, the succession in the second part of the trace, of increasingly better-formed polygonal spirals.

From their resemblance to the clothoids, I have called them pseudo-clothoids. Like the clothoids each of them has two origins, which are shared with the previous and with the following one.

Pseudo-clothoids do not form suddenly, initially using only one vector, they begin to form from the vector following, the one I call "hinge", which is therefore located between the two parts of the trace. The more the value of (b) increases and the more the part of the trace, composed of these "embryos" of pseudo-clothoids becomes longer, but also the number of the "finished" ones.

Some notes regarding the images that follow.

- The images inserted in this section all result, from formulation (1).
- Unless otherwise specified, all the traces resulting from the formulation (1), inserted in this manuscript, end with the last vector that converges, on the last origin that I call (Of).
- I did not consider it necessary to provide images of the divergent spiral, with which the traces, resulting from formulation (1) end. The important fact is that the origin of the spiral in question coincides with the second and last origin of the pseudo-clothoid that precedes it.
- The values of the convergence points inserted in Fig. 3 and Fig. 4, are calculated with the zeta(s) function of PARI-GP. They therefore correspond to the recognized convergence point, resulting from the Riemann zeta function, for that given value of (s).
- In the images I inserted an axis which, on condition that is $a=1/2$, divides the two parts of the trace crossing the hinge vector. Below I call the axis in question "axis of symmetry".
- Only for the traces resulting from formulation (1) and on the condition that $a=1/2$, the axis of symmetry can pass through the origin of the complex plane and cross the hinge vector. This happens when the last origin, coincides with the origin of the complex plane.
- In this manuscript I will highlight in various ways that, for the traces resulting from formulation (1), on condition that is $a=1/2$, the two parts of the trace are symmetrical to each other. The symmetry concerns the vertices of the vectors in the first part of the trace and the origins of the corresponding pseudo-clothoids in the second part.
- For the traces resulting from formulation (1), when $a \neq 1/2$ there is no complete symmetry, between the two parts of the trace, there is only the symmetry of orientations.
- The Riemann hypothesis is, strongly connected, to the situations described in the two previous points.
- In the images, I insert the axis of symmetry even when $a \neq 1/2$. I chose to position it so that it was useful, to highlight what happens when $a \neq 1/2$.
- The two different colors are, intended to distinguish, the two parts of the traces.

Fig. 1 represents three traces in which the value of (a) changes, while the value of (b), is known to be a zero of the zeta function.

In Fig. 1 and Fig. 2 I inserted the axes of the last four pseudo-clothoids. When $a \neq 1/2$ I have inserted (in a not exact but useful position) an axis of symmetry and dashed in brown a mirrored copy of the first four vectors. The purpose is to highlight that, when $a \neq 1/2$, only the symmetry of the orientations is maintained.

The real width of Fig. 2 is greater than the previous one, inserting it in the text it results differently resized, for this reason I remind you that the first vector, always has length 1.

Fig. 2 is constructed in the same way as the previous one, with respect to which I have slightly increased, the value of (b). Also in this case the value of (b), is known to be a zero of the zeta function. The aim is to show that when $a \neq 1/2$, not only does there not exist the correspondence, of the distances between the two origins of the pseudo-clothoids, with the length of the corresponding vectors in the first part of the trace, but the difference increases more and more, with the increase of the value of (b).

For Fig. 3 and Fig. 4 I have chosen (b), values such as to show opposite situations, to the traces represented in Fig. 1 and Fig. 2. Also in this case, for $a \neq 1/2$, I inserted in a not exact position (but I think useful) an axis of symmetry.

Also for Fig. 3 and Fig. 4, I have highlighted for $a=1/2$, (limiting myself to the first four, so as not to make the images confused) the symmetry between the start and end points of the vectors, present in the first part of the trace and the two origins of the pseudo-clothoids, present in the second part.

For Fig. 3 and Fig. 4, if you want to graphically identify, the position and inclination of the axis of symmetry you can do it, on condition that is $a=1/2$, using the point of convergence indicated in the images. It is necessary to trace a segment, from the origin of the complex plane to the point of convergence, after which it is sufficient to rotate the aforementioned segment by 90° , with the center in its middle point.

Having the axis of symmetry available, you can perform a mirrored copy with respect to it, of the vectors belonging to the first part of the trace. Observing the result starting from the symmetry axis, initially we notice an intertwining, of the mirrored vectors with the embryos of the pseudo-clothoid. Continuing towards the final part of the trace, we notice that the mirrored vectors, identify more and more clearly, the origins of the pseudo-clothoids.

What has just been described, can be best appreciated if the trace has been reconstructed using the CAD, or a software that allows enlargements such as to be able to evaluate the smallest details.

$\zeta(4/9 + 10025.59i) = 20.875575054129614421302629431834641558 + 0.14394712464019861910635743664665682775i$
 $\zeta(1/2 + 10025.59i) = 16.900400906635749063502159918611614548 + 0.16252322691469956117107095244179160737i$
 $\zeta(5/9 + 10025.59i) = 13.857189639663578203369308929074034010 + 0.17096830669277548178752799838936978523i$

$\zeta(4/9 + 100074.32i) = 32.329400048954922154521977284833503779 - 0.68868638503030944036989896762095780201i$
 $\zeta(1/2 + 100074.32i) = 24.466255804275120818399287427594376354 - 0.23915432432492810555908233572730219923i$
 $\zeta(5/9 + 100074.32i) = 18.890485466976571220454142515299938536 + 0.033055717971441902071244131928451116899i$

Dedicated to the trace resulting from formulation (1), I realized two methods, to calculate the coordinates of the last origin present in the trace.

The first method requires the presence, of a sufficiently formed last pseudo-clothoid in the trace. Uses the last vector of the last pseudo-clothoid and the first vector of the divergent spiral, with which the trace ends. Bases itself on the fact that the midpoints of these two vectors, compete for closest proximity to the last origin of the trace.

The precision of this method, is closely linked to the degree of formation of the last pseudo-clothoid of the trace and therefore to the value of (b), for example, to have a precision of the order of $1 \text{ E-}16$, a (b) value greater than thirty billion is required.

I would like to point out that this is the method, I use in this manuscript for the checks I propose.

In appendix (D) I explain how (starting from the first method) it is possible to calculate, the position of the last origin (O_f) more precisely. Unlike the second method, it can be used for values of (a) other than $1/2$, but at the moment the results are definitely better if $a > 0$.

The second method, also requires the presence of at least one spiral in the trace, consequently it must be $b \neq 0$. Uses four consecutive vectors of the last divergent spiral. The accuracy of the result depends only, on the distance from the start of the spiral, in number of vectors, of the four vectors used.

I don't use the second method in this manuscript, however I have dedicated a section to introduce it.

The second method, confirm that the final divergence, resulting from formulation (1), is due to a divergent spiral. Also highlights that the origin of the last divergent spiral, coincides with the second origin of the last pseudo-clothoid and also which coincides, with the resulting recognized convergence point for the same value of (s).

In the next sections I present some functions, the first five are the most important.

Like for the observations relating to the formulation (2), these first five functions also derive from the analysis of the obtained traces, analysis performed using the tools provided by the CAD.

The functions (4) and (5) are useful if $b \neq 0$ and allow you to calculate the length and the orientation of any vector, which is in position (n), of a trace resulting from formulation (1).

Functions (6), (7) and (8) allow you to identify the values of (n), corresponding to the three vectors, found in the key positions of a pseudo-clothoid. The resulting (n) values, are in function on the position of the pseudo-clothoid in the trace. Their usefulness increases for better formed pseudo-clothoids.

These functions are at the basis of the results, I obtained with my analysis method, the other functions I present in this manuscript derive from them.

4. For what reasons is Riemann hypothesis true, for the traces resulting from formulation (1).

The value of this section is conditioned, by the acceptance of the last origin of the trace, in alternative to the convergence point.

I point out that, even the points of convergence of formulations (2) and (3), are nothing other than the second origin of the last pseudo-clothoid, present in the traces resulting from these two formulations.

For those who are not willing to accept as a useful result, the last origin of the traces resulting from formulation (1), in section (11) I deal with the same topic, as regards the trace resulting from formulation (3).

The formulation (3) is not much different from formulation (1). After understand the reason why, the Riemann hypothesis is true for the traces resulting from formulation (1), the same reasons taking into account the differences, are valid for the traces resulting from formulation (3). In sections (11) and (12) I try to provide the necessary information, to enable the reader to be able to transfer, the reasons that are valid for formulation (1) to formulation (3).

SCH. 1 schematizes two traces resulting from formulation (1) for $a=1/2$, the two hypothetical values of (b) are such as to generate the two opposite situations, which can be found in the traces. In the two schematized traces, the pseudo-clothoids are replaced by their axes.

The trace represented on the left schematizes the situation of maximum extension.

The trace represented on the right schematizes the situation in which the axis of symmetry, as well as passing through the hinge vector intercepts the origin of the complex plane. Being the two parts of the trace in a situation of complete symmetry, the last origin of the trace coincides with the origin of the complex plane.

The value of (b) is the engine of the rotations, only if $a=1/2$ the value of (b) results neutral, with respect to the distances between the two origins of the pseudo-clothoids.

The distance between the two origins of a pseudo-clothoid derives from three parameters:

- 1 - From the length of the vectors that form it and therefore from (a).
- 2 and 3 - From the number of vectors that form it and therefore from (b) and its position in the trace (which I indicate below with (p)).

I remember that the symmetry concerns the vertices of the vectors in the first part of the trace and the origins of the corresponding pseudo-clothoids in the second part.

Like pseudo-clothoids, symmetry is also constantly improving, on the route to the last origin. To the reason why, the orientations of the axes of pseudo-clothoids are symmetrical, to the orientations of the corresponding vectors, in the first part of the trace, I dedicated section (7).

To the reason why, on condition that is $a=1/2$, the value of (b) results neutral with respects to the distance, between the two origins of the pseudo-clothoids, I dedicated section (9).

Below I summarize the three reasons, for which the Riemann hypothesis can only be true.

- First reason. In the traces resulting from any of the three formulations, for any value of (a) and for $b \geq 2\pi$, the orientations of the pseudo-clothoids are symmetrical, to the orientations of the vectors corresponding, in the first part of the trace. **The symmetry of the orientations, has the consequence that, the path of the second part of the trace, be guided by, the path of the first part of the trace.**
- Second reason. In the traces resulting from formulation (1), on condition that is $a=1/2$, the distances between the two origins of the pseudo-clothoids, are always equal, to the lengths of the corresponding vectors, in the first part of the trace. **The second reason completes the symmetry of the two parts of the trace.**
- The third reason reinforces the second. In the traces deriving from formulation (1), when $a \neq 1/2$, the distances between the two origins of the pseudo-clothoids are, influenced by the value of (b), **more and more evidently as the value of (b) increases.**

This influence is evident in two ways.

- If $a < 1/2$, the distance between the two origins of the pseudo-clothoids is always greater, than the length of the corresponding vectors, in the first part of the trace. **The second part of the trace is always longer than the first part.**
- If $a > 1/2$, the distance between the two origins of the pseudo-clothoids is always smaller, than the length of the corresponding vectors, in the first part of the trace. **The second part of the trace is always shorter than the first part.**

In this manuscript I highlight graphically (but not only) that the complete symmetry is present only in the traces resulting from formulation (1) and on condition that $a=1/2$. I add a further (simplified) verification by exploiting the fact that the axis of symmetry is also the bisector of the angle formed by the axis of the last pseudo-clothoid with the first vector of the trace. The data are (a) and (b) I recommend $b \geq 100000$ (it does not have to be a zero) and a segment from (Of) to the origin of the complex plane is needed. In this manuscript I provide the tools to calculate the orientation of the axis of symmetry and (Of). Even if for $b=100000$ the precision is not high, we begin to clearly notice that only if $a=1/2$, when (b) varies the axis of symmetry always remains perpendicular to the segment from (Of) to $0+0i$.

At this point I explained the reasons why, Riemann hypothesis can only be true, for the traces resulting from formulation (1). I would like to conclude this section by opening a parenthesis, to provide further arguments in favor of formulation (1).

If what I have graphically verified and what I highlight in this manuscript is true, then it must also be true that: The last origins of the trace resulting from formulation (1) coincide with the origin of the complex plane, only when three conditions occur.

- $a=1/2$ and $b \geq 2\pi$.
- The axis of symmetry passes through the origin of the complex plane.

In the case of traces resulting from formulation (1) and on condition that is $a=1/2$ and $b \geq 2\pi$, as the value of (b) varies, the symmetry axis passes in a point that varies non-randomly, of the hinge vector (I also find interesting the angle between the hinge vector and the axis of symmetry).

If $a=1/2$, given the value of (b) it is possible to calculate the value of (n) corresponding to the hinge vector, but also to establish in which point of the hinge vector, I can expect the axis of symmetry to pass.

Taking advantage of these two pieces of information, I can identify, with an accuracy that for now reaches the sixth decimal place, zero whose integer part goes to 16 digits. This means zero, a few tens of thousands of times larger, than those I found published on lmfdb.org.

The sixth decimal place is not much but it is a start. Between $b=1.000.000.000.000.000$ and $b=1.000.000.000.000.001$ I have identified the following five zero.

b=10000000000000000.092053...
b=10000000000000000.262139...

b=10000000000000000.555513...
b=10000000000000000.730076...

b=10000000000000000.888060...

Unfortunately, I fear that these zero are currently not verifiable in a short time. Here are other zero slightly larger than those I have found published on Imfdb.org until December 31, 2025.

Between b=30.610.047.000 and b=30.610.047.001 I have identified the following three zero

b=30610047000.092975...

b=30610047000.509201...

b=30610047000.574744...

After the last origin of the trace has been accepted, as a useful result of the Riemann zeta function, I publish the formula for calculating the value of (n) relating to the hinge vector and describe the method with which I have been able to identify, in few hours and with a normal p.c. the zero above.

In mid of 2025 I discovered the publication "Zeros number $10^{21}+1$ through $10^{21}+10^4$ of the Riemann zeta function", created by Professor Emeritus Andrew Odlyzko. I decided to compare my research method with the first zeros of this publication, which starts with 144176897509546973538.49806962.

To find large zeros I use two consecutive integers as reference, in this case 144176897509546973538 and 144176897509546973539. I divided the chosen interval into 100 parts and in this way I obtained the first two decimal places, I got the third decimal place by interpolation.

With this method I obtained nine zeros, of which the last five correspond to the first five of the publication in question. The first four I found are ...538.016 ...538.111 ...538.226 ...538.291.

It took my p.c. ~22 days to find the nine zeros, but it found them. I could never have achieved this result without the axis of symmetry and the hinge vector.

Searching for large zero is not the purpose of this manuscript, I wanted to show what I can do, to provide further argument in favor of the formulation (1) and the hinge vector.

What I have discovered and that I do not describe in this manuscript is valid only for the formulation (1), consequently it makes no sense to describe it, before the last origin of the trace has been accepted as, a useful result of the Riemann zeta function.

5. The first tools I equipped myself with.

To get the necessary results from PARI-GP, I created a custom function for each of the three formulations. The basis is the $\text{sum}(X=a, b, \text{espr})$ function of PARI-GP.

$$Z(f,s)=\text{sum}(n=1,f,1/n^s)$$

For the formulation (1)

$$Z(f,s)=\text{sum}(n=1,f,(-1)^n*n^(-s))/(2^(1-s)-1)$$

For the formulation (2)

$$Z(f,s)=\text{sum}(n=1,f,(-1)^n*n^(-s))$$

For the formulation (3)

These functions provide the value of $Z(f, s)$ for $n=f$, they are therefore a useful starting point but also need, to be able to extract the intermediate points of interest. The following command lines for PARI-GP are based on formulation (1) and get the values of $Z(f, s)$, for (n) from (f1) to (f2).

Note: Wanting to use the command lines (for PARI-GP) inserted in this manuscript, it's convenient to use copy/paste to transfer them to a text editor, where you can complete them before pasting them into PARI-GP. It may happen that the text editor changes some characters (e.g. " ^), this would cause an error in PARI-GP.

$$Z(f,s)= \text{sum}(n=1,f,1/n^s)$$

$$a=1/2$$

$$b=$$

$$s=a+b*I$$

$$f1=$$

$$f2=$$

$$\text{for}(f=f1,f2, \text{print}(Z(f,s)))$$

With these command lines it is therefore possible, to obtain the data necessary to report on the complex plane, or on the Cartesian plane, any part of the trace resulting from that of the three formulations, indicated in the first line.

6. Graphic analysis of the traces resulting from the formulation (1).

The following two functions give for a vector occupying position (n), the first the length $\rho(n)$ of the vector, the second the angle $\theta(n)$ that the vector makes with the real axis.

Given (a) in fractional form, if (nr) is its numerator and (dr) its denominator, the length $\rho(n)$ of each vector, is related to (n) by function (4).

$$\rho(n) = \frac{1}{\sqrt[n]{n^{nr}}} \quad (4)$$

Given the value of (b), the angle $\theta(n)$ that each vector forms with the real axis is related to (n) by the function (5).

$$\theta(n) = b \cdot \log(n) \quad (5)$$

Notes for function (4) and (5):

- It is understood that (n) is the value that determines the point of arrival of the vector, to which $\rho(n)$ and $\theta(n)$ refer.
- I point out that as (n) increases, the length of the vectors tends to increase if $a < 0$, remain constant if $a = 0$ and finally tends to decrease if $a > 0$.
- $\log(n)$ is the natural logarithm of (n).
- For (b) positive, at each increase of (b) the growth of $\theta(n)$ is clockwise, starting (zero) at 3.00.
- The resulting value for $\theta(n)$ is in radians.
- As the coefficient of the imaginary part of (s) and the value of (n) grow, the useful result of $\theta(n)$ is inevitably obtained net of the multiples of 2π .
- I point out that the two functions can also be applied, to the vectors belonging to the traces resulting from formulations (2) and (3), obviously taking into account the differences between the three formulations.

6.1 Pseudo-clothoids and their origins.

I have already highlighted that, the pseudo-clothoids of the second part of the trace gradually form starting from the hinge vector, their formation is due to the periodicity of the angles, but also to the trend of the curve $\theta(n)$, for a given value of (b).

Diag. 1.1 and Diag. 1.2 (the second on the following pages) reproduce the initial part of the $\theta(n)$ curve for the same value of (b). I rotate them 90° clockwise to take up less space.

In Diag. 1.1 I placed two red points on the $\theta(n)$ curve, which divide the curve into three parts. For the traces resulting from formulation (1), the first and the second parts correspond to the path that ends with the last origin, the third part corresponds to the divergent spiral that concludes the trace. Continuing, the $\theta(n)$ curve tends towards zero growth, it follows that the last divergent spiral has a step that tends to reach zero. The same effect is noted in the traces resulting from the other two formulations.

The $\theta(n)$ curve, which I have reported in the diagrams, has a fast-growing initial part, followed by a gradual slowdown in growth, in turn followed by growth tending to zero.

For $b \leq \pi$, the fast-growing initial part and the initial part of the gradual slowdown in growth, are not present in the curve $\theta(n)$, they appear with the increase in the value of (b) . Comparing the traces subject of this manuscript, with the curve $\theta(n)$, it is noted that the pseudo-clothoids are always formed, in the section of the curve that goes, from the beginning of the slowdown in growth, to the point where, the slowdown begins to become more evident. I think I can say that, the formation of the pseudo-clothoids requires an increase of $\theta(n)$, which is found only in that particular section of the curve. The pseudo-clothoids therefore derive from the harmony that occurs, between a particular increment of $\theta(n)$ and the periodicity of the angles.

From this harmony derives the connection that, pseudo-clothoids have, with a particular relationship between the value of (b) and the multiples of π .

Further on I present three functions which, taking advantage of this relationship, allow to calculate the values of (n) relating to the final points, of the first, of the last and of the medium vector of any pseudo-clothoid (sufficiently formed), belonging to the second part of the trace. In this manuscript I analyze the last pseudo-clothoids, the best formed.

With reference to Fig. 5, the first vector of a pseudo-clothoid, is the first that diverges from (D_p) , leaving it to its right. The last vector of a pseudo-clothoid, is the last one that converges on (C_p) , finding it to its left. (D_p) is the first origin of the pseudo-clothoid, (C_p) is the second origin. (p) indicates the position of the pseudo-clothoid, $p=1$ indicates the last pseudo-clothoid present in the trace.

Fig. 5 is extracted from a trace, resulting from formulation (1) for $s=1/2+5000.234317\dots i$, $n=143 \div 177$ and is the fifth counting from the last, therefore $p=5$.

The two vectors dotted in red in the two enlargements to the sides, are, on the right the last vector of the previous pseudo-clothoid and on the left, the first vector of the following one.

For positive (b) , the divergence from (D_p) is always clockwise and convergence on (C_p) is always counterclockwise. When $p=1$, the second origin I call (O_f) , but sometimes also $C_1=O_f$.

The Fig. 5 allows us to highlight, a further characteristic of pseudo-clothoids. As the value of (b) increases and the closer the vectors are to the origins, plus the comparison of the orientations of two consecutive vectors approaches π radians, net of the multiples of 2π .

As the value of (b) increases and the closer the vectors are to the point (M_p) , plus the comparison of the orientations of two consecutive vectors approaches zero radians, net of the multiples of 2π . It can also be noted that, in correspondence of point (M_p) , the divergence from the first origin ends and begins the convergence towards the second origin.

Note: I call "axis" with reference to a pseudo-clothoid, a segment joining the two origins.

The angle α formed by the vector ending in (M_p) , with the axis of the pseudo-clothoid, tends to $\pi/4$ radians, as the value of (b) increases.

When I calculate the value of (n) , corresponding to the first or last vector of a pseudo-clothoid, I want to get an integer value, for this reason the result of the calculation must be rounded.

In Fig. 5 it can already be noted that, the closest proximity to the origins of the pseudo-clothoids, is always disputed by the midpoints, of the last vector that converges there and of the first vector, that diverges from the same origin.

If not rounded, the result of the above calculation indicates which of the two vectors, has its midpoint closest to the origin.

If the decimal part, of the result of the calculation in question is less than 0.5, the closest to the origin, is the midpoint of the last vector that converges, on the contrary, is the midpoint of the first that diverges.

Figs. 6 and 7, show the trajectories of the midpoints of the vectors towards and from the origins. The parts of traces used concern the point (Of), resulting from the formulation (1) for $s=1/2+10000.065345...i$.

Both images in Fig. 6 and Fig. 7, are an enlargement of the trace, those on the right are a further enlargement, of the central part of the images on the left.

Fig. 6 uses the last hundred vectors ($n=3083\div 3183$) that converge on (Of), Fig. 7 uses the first hundred vectors ($n=3183\div 3283$) that diverge from (Of). I added a small circle to indicate the origin and two spirals obtained by connecting the midpoints of the vectors.

It can be seen that the spirals traced in the two images, by connecting the midpoints of the vectors, are almost superimposable.

For both images, in brown are the vectors for which their final point corresponds to (n) even, in green are the vectors for which their final point corresponds to (n) odd.

What happens is that the angle between two consecutive vectors, tightens more and more around the origin, until it reaches the inversion and subsequent enlargement of the angle.

Note: The same behavior of the vectors is found in the origins that precede (Of), but also in the origins that precede the last one, in the traces resulting from formulations (2) and (3).

- Three functions that allow to calculate, for a given pseudo-clothoid, the values of (n) corresponding to the first, last and intermediate vector. Valid for formulation (1).

The value of (n) corresponds to the end point of the vector and (p) is the position of the pseudo-clothoid, p=1 corresponds to the last pseudo-clothoid.

Last vector (rounding to the previous integer)
$$n(p) = \frac{b}{\pi \cdot (2 \cdot p - 1)} \quad (6)$$

Point (M_p) (rounding to the nearest integer)
$$n(p) = \frac{b}{2 \cdot \pi \cdot p} \quad (7)$$

First vector (rounding to the next integer)
$$n(p) = \frac{b}{\pi \cdot (2 \cdot p + 1)} \quad (8)$$

From functions (6), (7) and (8) it is evident that the divisor of (b), for p=1 is: $\pi, 2\pi, 3\pi$, for p=2 is $3\pi, 4\pi, 5\pi$, and so on (as long as the increase of (p) is useful).

In appendix (C) I present a further evidence of symmetry and confirmation of the three functions.

These three functions concern the part of the $\theta(n)$ curve where the pseudo-clothoids can be formed. The evidence discussed in this manuscript concerns the last pseudo-clothoids, the best formed ones.

The first purpose of Diag. 1.2, is to graphically highlight the two reasons why, the number of vectors that form the pseudo-clothoids, starting with one, increases as the value of (n) increases. The first reason is the growth mode of the $\theta(n)$ curve, highlighted by its curvature and black colored circles. Each black circle corresponds, on the trace, to the endpoint of a vector. The second reason is highlighted by the red colored circles, their position results from functions (6) and (8). The second purpose of Diag. 1.2, is to highlight how the value of (b) affects the pseudo-clothoids. For the second purpose I added two more $\theta(n)$ curves.

The increase of (b) produces a lengthening, of the first two parts of the $\theta(n)$ curve. The lengthening of the first part of the curve, in addition to increase the number of vector in the first part of the trace, for $a > 0$, reduces the length of the vectors that form the pseudo-clothoids. The lengthening of the second part of the curve, in addition to increase the number of pseudo-clothoids in the second part of the trace, increases also the number of vectors that form the last pseudo-clothoids. I note that for $a > 0$, the increase of (b) produces last pseudo-clothoids, composed by a greater number of shorter vectors, therefore better formed.

- Command lines for PARI-GP useful for identifying the origins of pseudo-clothoids, in the traces resulting from formulation (1).

```

a=
b=
p=
s=a+b*I
x1=b/(Pi*(2*p-1))
x2=truncate(b/(Pi*(2*p-1)))
Z(f,s)=sum(n=1,f,1/n^s)
if((x1-x2) < 0.5, f1=truncate(b/(Pi*(2*p-1)))-1, f1=truncate(b/(Pi*(2*p-1))))
f2=f1+1
z1=Z(f1,s)
z2=Z(f2,s)
Cp=(real(z1)+real(z2))/2+((imag(z1)+imag(z2))/2)*I

```

The requested data are (a), (b) and (p).

The difference between (x1) and (x2) determines which of the two vectors, has its midpoint closest to the origin, I remember that the two vectors are the last one that converges on the origin and the first one that diverges from it. In the previous command lines, (f2) is the value of (n) corresponding to the endpoint of the vector, whose midpoint results closest to the origin.

(z1) and (z2) are the extremes of the vector used and (C_p) is the midpoint which I assume as the origin
 $C_p = D_{p-1}$.

When the searched origin is the last of the trace then p=1. The two vectors that in this case, contend the greatest proximity to (Of), result from b/π .

The customized function Z(f,s) has the drawback of starting over from 1, at each increment of the value of (n). For values of (b) which involve long times, I use the following variant of the command lines.

I somehow solved the problem, by calculating a value (Base) just smaller than (z1).

```

a=
b=
p=
s=a+b*I
x1=b/(Pi*(2*p-1))
x2=truncate(b/(Pi*(2*p-1)))
Z(f,s)=sum(n=1,f,1/n^s)
if((x1-x2) < 0.5, f1=truncate(b/(Pi*(2*p-1)))-1, f1=truncate(b/(Pi*(2*p-1))))
f2=f1+1
fb1=f1-2
fb2=f1-1
Base=Z(fb1,s)
Z(f,s)=Base+sum(n=fb2,f,1/n^s)
z1=Z(f1,s)
z2=Z(f2,s)
Cp=(real(z1)+real(z2))/2+((imag(z1)+imag(z2))/2)*I

```

- Distance between the two origins of a pseudo-clothoid. Function valid for formulation (1).

This function, for the traces resulting from formulation (1) and only if $a=1/2$, allows to calculate the distance between the two origins of a pseudo-clothoid.

$$r(p) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{p}} \quad (9)$$

I derived it from function (4) by replacing (n) with (p), however I point out that only the square root is expected in this function. In function (4) the root is square only if $a=1/2$.

In another way it is possible to calculate $r(p)$ when $a \neq 1/2$. In this case I use the following command lines for PARI-GP.

With these command lines, starting from the resulting value of $r(p)$ for $a=1/2$, the distance between the two origins of the pseudo-clothoid is obtained, given the values of (b), (p) and $a \neq 1/2$.

```
b=
p=
nr=
dr=
medio=b/(2*Pi*p)    \\ In this case, rounding would be counterproductive.
rBase=1/sqrt(p)
rho1=1/sqrt(medio)
rho2=1/sqrtn(medio^nr,dr)
rpb=(rho2/rho1)*rBase
```

Note: I called (rpb) the distance between the two origins of the pseudo-clothoids, calculated in this way, to distinguish it from the one that can be calculated when $a=1/2$. When I use this method below, (rpb) becomes for example (r1b), if the result refers to the last pseudo-clothoid.

As for function (4), (nr) and (dr) used in the penultimate line, are the numerator and denominator of (a), expressed in fractional form.

- Inclination and position of the axis of symmetry.

In the traces resulting from any of the three formulations, the axis of symmetry always divides into two equal parts, the angle between the axis of the last pseudo-clothoid and the first vector. Also divides into two equal parts the angles, between the axes of the other pseudo-clothoids and the corresponding vectors, in the first part of the trace.

For the traces resulting from the formulation (1), if $a=1/2$ and the last origin (Of) does not coincide with the origin of the complex plane, the axis is perpendicular to a segment which joins (Of) with the origin of the complex plane. The intersection point corresponds to the middle point of the same segment.

If $a=1/2$ and the last origin (Of) coincides with the complex plane, the axis passes through the origin of the plane.

If $a \neq 1/2$ is necessary to remember that, the symmetry concerns only the orientations.

For the traces resulting from formulation (1), when the last origin does not coincide with the origin of the complex plane, I have chosen to position the symmetry axis so that it crosses the hinge vector, regardless of the value of (a). This choice is due to the need to have the axis of symmetry, in a position as central as possible in the image.

To calculate the inclination of the axis of symmetry, it is necessary to know the inclination of the last pseudo-clothoid.

For values of (b) higher than a few tens of millions and with reference to the last pseudo clothoid, the angle Alpha that I indicated in Fig. 5 is already very close to $\pi/4$ and therefore can be used.

For lower values of (b) and in cases in which (Of) coincides with the origin of the complex plane, the method that I find to be the most accurate, is to use the PARI-GP zeta(s) function, to locate two points of convergence very close to and astride the origin of the complex plane. I therefore determine the inclination of the axis of symmetry, for these two cases and I use a value halfway between the two.

Note: As regards the origins of pseudo-clothoids, except in section 10 (which concern the last origin), I refer to the use of the midpoint of the vector that is closest to the origin. This is the first of the two methods that I present in this manuscript.

To show how the precision, with which I determine the origins of the pseudo-clothoids, increases as the value of (b) increases, in the tests that follow I use increasing values of (b), starting from $b=10000.065345\dots$ up to $b=30384448732.364055\dots$

When the value of (b) is large enough, I use the following command lines for PARI-GP with which I calculate (in decimal degrees) the inclination of the symmetry axis, which I call Gamma. As for the vectors the zero is at 3.00 and for (b) positive the increase is clockwise.

```
b=  
p=1  
n(p)=round(b/(2*Pi*p))  
ThetaM(p)=b*log(n(p))  
ThetaMp=ThetaM(p)*180/Pi-(truncate((ThetaM(p)*180/Pi)/360)*360)  
Beta=ThetaMp-45  
Gamma=(Beta+180)/2 \\ It can even be Gamma=(Beta-180)/2
```

As data only (b) is required, in these command lines, n(p) has the same role that in function (5) it is played by (n), n(p) is calculated using function (7).

The angle ThetaMp, is obtained by transforming ThetaM(p) into decimal degrees and removing the multiples of 360°.

6.2 Verification of the method of calculating the origins of pseudo-clothoids.

Below I present a series of images, followed by the values I have calculated for the points highlighted in the images, the aim is to provide concrete results of what I have described.

With these checks, in addition to the two symmetries, I want to show the improvement of the precision with which I determine, the position of the last origin (Of). Starting from a precision corresponding to the eighth decimal place, I arrive at a precision corresponding to the sixteenth decimal place.

When larger zero are available, you can continue with the check.

To create Fig. 8, I used function (6) to extract the last three pseudo-clothoids, from the trace generated by formulation (1), by $s=1/2+10000.065345\dots i$.

In the image I inserted, the axes of the pseudo clothoids, the first three vectors, the symmetry axis, the measures of the angles and the initial and final value of (n) relating to the last three pseudo-clothoids.

These are the values I calculated for the indicated points.

$Z1=1 + 0*i$
 $Z2=1.279971387669553166543348050340939 - 0.649319660942424238508940891522691*i$
 $Z3=0.703209915488297883915190006009985 - 0.623251720083115422214226205648555*i$
 $\rho1=1/\sqrt{1}=1$
 $\rho2=1/\sqrt{2}=0.70710678118654752440084436210484903928$
 $\rho3=1/\sqrt{3}=0.57735026918962576450914878050195745565$
 $C1=Of=0.000000001656863602895482185076358 - 0.00000870728994730116277388661119*i$
 $D1=C2=-0.965345475328091939805484497624280 + 0.260980551504779560828553363922483*i$
 $D2=C3=-1.404988439711474889002277216208724 - 0.292816533905999643841026045005520*i$
 $D3=C4=-0.841636966379357619953239167296504 - 0.418077650468387878482817491565836*i$
 $r1=1.0000015963419633007658231096434332396$
 $r2=0.70709062215622857589281981925590547340$
 $r3=0.57710937423327603288955743178562614204$

Fig. 9 is constructed like Fig. 8 and presents the same information. In (s) only the value of (b) changes. $s=1/2+100000.743723\dots i$

These are the values I calculated for the indicated points.

$$Z1=1 + 0*i$$

$$Z2=1.457719102883924466831745848365844 + 0.538974232088265393013052030027273*i$$

$$Z3=1.949672352173808132843522238529594 + 0.236789960746325907222725029908105*i$$

$$\rho1=1/\sqrt{1}=1$$

$$\rho2=1/\sqrt{2}=0.70710678118654752440084436210484903928$$

$$\rho3=1/\sqrt{3}=0.57735026918962576450914878050195745565$$

$$C1=Of=-0.000000037040110100466592765668563 + 0.00000009152152648327514216743411*i$$

$$D1=C2=0.287254654866922087764470656216460 - 0.957853802713809535614926211859966*i$$

$$D2=C3=-0.097522918532458818642275418447890 - 1.551103336881141503649659434053874*i$$

$$D3=C4=0.333245554643230822458265974168000 - 1.935524540314814773299815774745003*i$$

$$r1=0.99999959146429558010392354593870939209$$

$$r2=0.70710592613898544602740375870939454761$$

$$r3=0.57735702916956718654887616656953995788$$

Note: Due to the significant increase in the number of vectors, deriving from the values of (b) that I use to make the next images, from now on I will draw only the axes of the pseudo-clothoids.

Fig. 10 concerns a trace resulting from the formulation (1) for $s=1/2+ 500000.710151\dots i$

$$Z(f,s)=\sum(n=1,f,1/n^s)$$

$$s=1/2+500000.710151\dots i$$

These are the values that I have calculated for the indicated points.

$Z_1=1 + 0*i$
 $Z_2=1.700592908841963041729518549224089 + 0.095757903487685357863589224616525*i$
 $Z_3=2.192506617124496826584513799376035 + 0.398006537789082302598958919957756*i$
 $\rho_1=1/\sqrt{1}=1$
 $\rho_2=1/\sqrt{2}=0.70710678118654752440084436210484903928$
 $\rho_3=1/\sqrt{3}=0.57735026918962576450914878050195745565$
 $C_1=Of=-0.000000002779215499238527530197103 + 0.00000000727352149747625967257733*i$
 $D_1=C_2=0.912186423676250091635914663206452 - 0.409775348567324417765620230872246*i$
 $D_2=C_3=1.512018607332847513810560650738484 - 0.784210128866917253542525463440716*i$
 $D_3=C_4=1.836882213688976626024759987444427 - 1.261491752775133371360414491054648*i$
 $r_1=0.99999995674958242614842959779764096643$
 $r_2=0.70710681883874261987046146629742942055$
 $r_3=0.57735094288930876105294711519002247900$

Fig. 11 concerns a trace resulting from the formulation (1) for $s=1/2+ 2000000000.333438\dots i$

These are the values that I have calculated for the indicated points.

$Z_1 = 1 + 0 \cdot i$

$Z_2 = -1.262632494756541500146249888829203 - 0.656524312343385499266864477784058 \cdot i$

$Z_3 = 0.852749217294522995093719678260941 - 0.249917583193058615072419945469997 \cdot i$

$\rho_1 = 1/\sqrt{1} = 1$

$\rho_2 = 1/\sqrt{2} = 0.70710678118654752440084436210484903928$

$\rho_3 = 1/\sqrt{3} = 0.57735026918962576450914878050195745565$

$C_1 = Of = -2.1018598982344225278283959075 \cdot 10^{-14} + 1.2461516514710634043133623700 \cdot 10^{-14} \cdot i$

$D_1 = C_2 = -0.981276543078059672283529814644184 - 0.192604117309454072600458549454328 \cdot i$

$D_2 = C_3 = -1.112542363961832134698197927175510 - 0.887420124800682799411170744861789 \cdot i$

$D_3 = C_4 = -0.788647648547555736194119162544608 - 0.409481272372406946812874299658904 \cdot i$

$r_1 = 0.9999999999987229790352673921371217883$

$r_2 = 0.70710678118537503454176497881172460539$

$r_3 = 0.57735026918998863498291843250261601856$

Fig. 12 concerns a trace resulting from the formulation (1) for $s = 1/2 + 30384448732.364055...i$

These are the values that I have calculated for the indicated points.

$Z_1=1 + 0*i$
 $Z_2=0.724519368924790938343312247422888 + 0.651237607868590893366274041132017*i$
 $Z_3=0.178532541700720327413478654136258 + 0.463536468204692740166196202618637*i$
 $\rho_1=1/\sqrt{1}=1$
 $\rho_2=1/\sqrt{2}=0.70710678118654752440084436210484903928$
 $\rho_3=1/\sqrt{3}=0.57735026918962576450914878050195745565$
 $C_1=Of=6.3551578879780175364007735183 \text{ E-16} - 5.5733444776495422447224959487 \text{ E-17}*i$
 $D_1=C_2=0.875065558444772233553291409223290 + 0.484004409508565235812290240260185*i$
 $D_2=C_3=0.949203820018410592013826525126720 - 0.219205031675801220002712958090326*i$
 $D_3=C_4=0.380581372882963358738369312836549 - 0.319214260985179251496374622206244*i$
 $r_1=0.999999999999747271997531593516918605$
 $r_2=0.70710678118654057191979551222158032576$
 $r_3=0.57735026918964906754505400912423534885$

- What changes if $a \neq 1/2$.

If (a) is different from 1/2, the distances between the two origins of the pseudo-clothoids, no result more only in function of (p), but are influenced by the value of (b). This influence increases as (b) increases.

I remind again that even when $a \neq 1/2$, the symmetry remains between the orientations of the pseudo-clothoids and the orientations of the corresponding vectors in the first part of the trace.

Always using traces deriving from formulation (1), for the next images I change the value of (a). For a comparison, I use the same values of (b) already used for Fig. 8 and Fig. 9, for (a) I use 4/9 and 5/9.

Fig. 13 concerns a trace resulting from the formulation (1) for $s=4/9+10000.065345...i$.

For a comparison, when $a \neq 1/2$ I add the result given by the zeta(s) function of PARI-GP. I recall that this result corresponds, to the point of convergence for formulation (2).

These are the values I calculated for the indicated points.

$Z_1=1 + 0*i$
 $Z_2=1.290962847660521008432650356690127 - 0.674811448278282790179477060884931*i$
 $Z_3=0.677902851617155069656615670941578 - 0.647102919725522173337019895689558*i$
 $\rho_1=1/\sqrt[9]{1^4, 9}=1$
 $\rho_2=1/\sqrt[9]{2^4, 9}=0.73486724613779942569210434909166210696$
 $\rho_3=1/\sqrt[9]{3^4, 9}=0.61368584903291603508168767420564100200$
 $C_1=Of=0.078069391208961165037678213752753 + 0.307906226690245588368501576278479*i$
 $D_1=C_2=-1.375922409635182348505531827444396 + 0.700992286079078689342785639887135*i$
 $D_2=C_3=-2.013094019370784046672524074146321 - 0.101620100266519179114611683748904*i$
 $D_3=C_4=-1.214818387997969490951889594343979 - 0.279113183742634579261078366946870*i$
 $r_{1b}=1.5061875514552878274959500761833515671$
 $r_{2b}=1.0248024792037427678003416878700458546$
 $r_{3b}=0.81810997914151621963050311883954803174$
 $\zeta(4/9+10000.065345...i)$
 $=-0.078069316066729723355353601968168 + 0.307907492738082014484678512957571*i$

Fig. 14 concerns a trace resulting from the formulation (1) for $s=5/9+10000.065345...i$.

These are the values I have calculated for the indicated points.

$Z_1=1 + 0*i$
 $Z_2=1.269395142863975603839539912109236 - 0.624790855522824844820086729917940*i$
 $Z_3=0.726783003857016117828109842126264 - 0.600266365189442657817308538178919*i$
 $\rho_1=1/\sqrt[9]{1^5, 9}=1$
 $\rho_2=1/\sqrt[9]{2^5, 9}=0.68039500008718848212784018766240654944$
 $\rho_3=1/\sqrt[9]{3^5, 9}=0.54316607407294877966782901238146633121$
 $C_1=Of=-0.003314743587799824311241490466120 - 0.210871589766428974340592177894236*i$
 $D_1=C_2=-0.644234424726251896080264837547347 - 0.037598519000937387673623507097398*i$
 $D_2=C_3=-0.947584172934760675868364210073238 - 0.419714818552751761969187061345085*i$
 $D_3=C_4=-0.550021125427088370760360697399167 - 0.508114462470384641799983996118217*i$
 $r_{1b}=0.66392794113441831924094269421957823048$
 $r_{2b}=0.48789889773538899506180447578843385952$
 $r_{3b}=0.40744318225175140476662413531467566286$
 $\zeta(5/9+10000.065345...i)$
 $=-0.003314715037153960399700583461078 - 0.210870993947408577649344658439441*i$

Fig. 15 concerns a trace resulting from the formulation (1) for $s=4/9+ 100000.743723...i$.

These are the values I have calculated for the indicated points.

$$Z1 = 1 + 0 \cdot i$$

$$Z2 = 1.475688800603137041590117824682802 + 0.560133943291157827931177315009343 \cdot i$$

$$Z3 = 1.998603162276026501168442363805462 + 0.238931683555200232567194497996355 \cdot i$$

$$\rho1 = 1/\sqrt[4]{9} = 1$$

$$\rho2 = 1/\sqrt[4]{2^4 \cdot 9} = 0.73486724613779942569210434909166210696$$

$$\rho3 = 1/\sqrt[4]{3^4 \cdot 9} = 0.61368584903291603508168767420564100200$$

$$C1 = Of = -0.846730213815135417144312542193614 + 0.768322636867214696402480283034644 \cdot i$$

$$D1 = C2 = -0.355028468975026372039929691617218 - 0.871262086475091331518718032013581 \cdot i$$

$$D2 = C3 = -0.988782182746016600743940476082647 - 1.848382717198140525681412140555477 \cdot i$$

$D3=C4=-0.295081980444689918852089559870696 - 2.467446172875333732375280340338790*i$
 $r1b=1.7117275128333209138072851381533823726$
 $r2b=1.1646508412434703068103081075350967919$
 $r3b=0.92975231302832797031983434662838644617$
 $\text{zeta}(4/9+100000.743723...*i)$
 $=-0.846730149507570968719373810221128 + 0.768322624638156318560220410299009*i$

Fig. 16 concerns a trace resulting from the formulation (1) for $s=5/9+ 100000.743723...i$.

These are the values I have calculated for the indicated points.

$Z1=1 + 0*i$
 $Z2=1.440428231396715774371922260021345 + 0.518613853587046207062557111660290*i$
 $Z3=1.903253537461400721244212443489882 + 0.234321539076170299965132534437333*i$
 $\rho1=1/\sqrt[5]{9}=1$
 $\rho2=1/\sqrt[5]{2^5 \cdot 9}=0.68039500008718848212784018766240654944$
 $\rho3=1/\sqrt[5]{3^5 \cdot 9}=0.54316607407294877966782901238146633121$
 $C1=O_f=0.572034888482650853911492699453535 - 0.344879910580041649508544771687717*i$
 $D1=C2=0.739850576750366317029246434750709 - 0.904463019168379733376794300908496*i$
 $D2=C3=0.506236523862801265649700878040195 - 1.264648860955369163723195494310002*i$
 $D3=C4=0.773731736022865961573792846330884 - 1.503363738414937802577330865007652*i$
 $r1b=0.58420513341212783192918541347107579981$
 $r2b=0.42931321757013609472032176868340751960$
 $r3b=0.35851842330740965210028708609210130873$
 $\text{zeta}(5/9+100000.743723...*i)$
 $=-0.572034909804820210912224639256731 - 0.344879917005207774003068196284908*i$

7. For what reason the orientations of the axes of the pseudo-clothoids, are symmetrical, to the orientations of the corresponding vectors, in the first part of the trace.

Note: In this section I refer exclusively to the traces resulting from formulation (1). The results of the following function are in radians.

Before considering the topic of this section, it is necessary to present some functions.

I remember that the function (5) shows that the orientations of the vectors, depend exclusively on the values of (b) and (n), the same is also valid for the orientations of the pseudo-clothoids, with (p) that replacing (n).

From functions (5) and (7) is deduced the function that allow us to obtain, the orientation of the vectors that end in the points (M_p).

The rounding comes from the fact that (M_p), must correspond to an integer.

$$\theta M(p) = b \cdot \log \left(\text{round} \left(\frac{b}{2 \cdot \pi \cdot p} \right) \right) \quad (10)$$

$\log()$ is the natural logarithm.

When I described the pseudo-clothoid, in Fig. 5 I highlighted the Alpha angle, in this section I indicate it with the corresponding Greek letter. I remember that it is the angle between the vector that ends at point (M_p) and the axis of the pseudo-clothoid to which it belongs.

Subtracting (α) from function (10), you get the function that approximates the orientation $\beta(p)$, of the pseudo-clothoids. We need to talk about approximation because, as I have already written in section (6.1), (α) does not have a fixed value, but clearly shows that it tends to $\pi/4$ as (b) increases.

I remember that it must be $p \geq 1$, the maximum value of (p) is linked to the value of (b), the larger is (b) and the larger can be (p).

$$\beta(p) = b \cdot \log \left(\text{round} \left(\frac{b}{2 \cdot \pi \cdot p} \right) \right) - \alpha \quad (11)$$

The sign (-) in front of (α), derives from the fact that the axis of the pseudo-clothoid is always delayed, by the angle (α), with respect to the direction of growth (clockwise for positive (b)) of the orientation of the vector that ends in (M_p).

- Axis of symmetry.

What I call the axis of symmetry, arises as the bisector of the angle between the first vector and the axis of the last pseudo-clothoid.

Widening your gaze, the simple bisector becomes the axis of symmetry, between the orientations of the axes of the pseudo-clothoids and the corresponding vectors in the first part of the trace. Only if $a=1/2$, does the symmetry also concern lengths and distances.

The following function, provides the approximation of the orientation (γ) of the symmetry axis. Regarding the approximation, what I has already been highlighted for function (11) is valid.

$$\gamma = \frac{\pm \pi + b \cdot \log \left(\text{round} \left(\frac{b}{2 \cdot \pi} \right) \right) - \alpha}{2} \quad (12)$$

Note for function (12): The presence of $\pm\pi$, resolves the fact that the first vector of the trace always has the same orientation, while the orientation of the axis of the last pseudo-clothoid can have any value. It is also necessary to consider the fact that the first vector move away from the origin, while the last pseudo-clothoid reaches the last origin. The apparent lack of $\theta(n)$ derives from the fact that, the angle $\theta(n)$ of the first vector of the trace, is always zero radians.

An acceptable description, of the symmetry axis of the trace, could be the following.

The bisector between the orientation of the first vector of the trace and the axis of the last pseudo-clothoid, is also the axis to which tend to be symmetrical, the orientations of the pairs made up of the axes of the pseudo-clothoids and the vectors corresponding to them in the first part of the trace.

- For what reason the orientations are symmetrical.

I remember that the function (5) furnish, given (b), the orientation of any vector of the trace, corresponding to position (n). The function (11) furnish, given (b), the orientation of a pseudo-clothoid that is, in position (p).

The reason why the orientation results symmetrical, derives from the fact that given the same (b), the diagrams of the two functions in question, are symmetrical to each other.

In the case in question, the second part of the trace is formed by a succession of polygonal spirals (pseudo-clothoid) which in turn are formed by vectors whose lengths and orientations can be calculated with the functions (4) and (5). The values of (n) corresponding to the vectors from which the orientations of the pseudo-clothoids are obtained, can be calculated with the function (7). Denying the symmetry between the orientations of the vectors and the corresponding pseudo-clothoids in the two parts of the trace, means denying the validity of the functions (5) and (7), but also of the functions (6) and (8).

I now propose an equivalent verification, to the comparison of the diagrams of the two functions in question.

Being the results furnish by function (11), approximate due to (α), I do not use the function (11) but function (10). I have ascertained that the lack of (α), does not affect the validity of the verify.

Formula (13) that I use for verification, adds the results of functions (5) and (10), the requested data are (b), (n) and (p). Given the same (b) and varying the pairs of values $n=p$, the result (K) of formula (13) remains constant, when the functions (5) and (10) compensate each other. The constant value of (K) result removing the multiples of 2π .

Verify that the lack of (α) in formula (13), does not compromise its validity.

For $a=1/2$ and using (b) values between 2000 and 2000000, chosen so that the last origin did not fall, on the origin of the complex plane, I performed the following check.

- I used the command lines, I placed in this manuscript after formula (13). Using $n=p$ values from 1 to 10, I obtained the first ten results of (K) for different values of (b). I then also calculated the differences between consecutive results.
- Using the same (b) values, I graphically obtained the (α) values relating to the last ten pseudo-clothoids, calculating also the differences between consecutive results.

The results obtained highlighted the following.

- The series of results of the two methods are equal, within the limits of precision obtainable graphically.
- The differences of the consecutive value, show in both cases, to oscillate around the zero value.

In conclusion, from this verification I draw two considerations.

- The lack of (α) in formula (13), does not influence the meaning of the results.
- I believe the oscillation of the results obtained, is due to the rounding necessary, to calculate (M_p) and to the fact that increasing the value of (p) given the same (b), results fewer and longer the vectors that form the pseudo-clothoid.

I want to remind you that, the precision with which a pseudo-clothoid is formed, derives from the number and length of the vectors that form it and therefore from the combination of the (b) and (p) values.

Notes relating to formula (13) and the command lines that follow.

- Given two orientations, the orientation of their bisector is equal to the half of their sum. The function (12) and the verification method I chose, derive from this simple observation.
- Below formula (13), I report the command lines for PARI-GP that I used, I highlight that in some cases, it is necessary to increase the calculation precision (in my tests I used `\p 200`).
- The command lines, in addition to carrying out the calculation corresponding to formula (13), present the result net of the multiples of 2π .
- The larger the value of (b), the number of sufficiently formed pseudo-clothoids increases. This does not mean that the verification, only works for very large values of (b). However, it is necessary to take into account the fact that, decreasing the value of (b) given the same (p) decreases the number of vectors that form the pseudo-clothoids. Fewer are the vectors, the more the result is affected by the rounding.

In the results I limited the number of decimals, to those for which there is correspondence. I chose the second value of (b), sufficiently large, so that the following was revealed and highlighted.

Fixed the value of (b), increasing the value of $n=p$ reduces the number of decimals corresponding, between two consecutive results of (K). *In an equivalent way it can be stated that, the closer the value of $n=p$ gets to 1, the more increases the number of decimals corresponding, between two consecutive results of (K).*

In the formula (13), given the value of (b) I can change the value of (p) and (n), which must be equal to each other.

When (net of multiples of 2π) the result (K) does not change, it means that the variations of $\theta(n)$ and $\theta M(p)$ have compensated. The compensation is the confirmation of the symmetry of the orientations, so I can state the following.

Within the limits in were the result (K) does not change, the symmetry of the orientations is verified.

The required equality between (n) and (p), serves to achieve the correspondence, between vector and pseudo-clothoid.

$$b \cdot \log(n) + b \cdot \log\left(\frac{b}{2 \cdot \pi \cdot p}\right) = K \quad (13)$$

Here are the command lines. I filled them in by inserting the values of (b), (n) and (p), who produced one of the series of results, reported below.

```

\p 200
b=1111111333344444444445555555
n=p=10
Tn=b*log(n)
Tp=b*log(round(b/(2*Pi*p)))
TT=(Tn+Tp)-(truncate((Tn+Tp)/(2*Pi))*(2*Pi))
S1=Str("n=p=" n " K=" TT)
n=p=20
Tn=b*log(n)
Tp=b*log(round(b/(2*Pi*p)))
TT=(Tn+Tp)-(truncate((Tn+Tp)/(2*Pi))*(2*Pi))
S2=Str("n=p=" n " K=" TT)
n=p=30
Tn=b*log(n)
Tp=b*log(round(b/(2*Pi*p)))
TT=(Tn+Tp)-(truncate((Tn+Tp)/(2*Pi))*(2*Pi))
S3=Str("n=p=" n " K=" TT)
n=p=40
Tn=b*log(n)
Tp=b*log(round(b/(2*Pi*p)))
TT=(Tn+Tp)-(truncate((Tn+Tp)/(2*Pi))*(2*Pi))
S4=Str("n=p=" n " K=" TT)
n=p=50
Tn=b*log(n)
Tp=b*log(round(b/(2*Pi*p)))
TT=(Tn+Tp)-(truncate((Tn+Tp)/(2*Pi))*(2*Pi))
S5=Str("n=p=" n " K=" TT)
b=Str("b=" b)
print(b " " S1 "\n" b " " S2 "\n" b " " S3 "\n" b " " S4 "\n" b " " S5)

```

```

b=123456789012345 n=p=1 K=3.51304065297
b=123456789012345 n=p=2 K=3.51304065297
b=123456789012345 n=p=3 K=3.51304065297
b=123456789012345 n=p=4 K=3.51304065297
b=123456789012345 n=p=5 K=3.51304065297

```

```

b=1111111333344444444445555555 n=p=1 K=3.540111614032122353696843
b=1111111333344444444445555555 n=p=2 K=3.540111614032122353696843
b=1111111333344444444445555555 n=p=3 K=3.540111614032122353696843
b=1111111333344444444445555555 n=p=4 K=3.540111614032122353696843
b=1111111333344444444445555555 n=p=5 K=3.540111614032122353696843

```

```

b=1111111333344444444445555555 n=p=10 K=3.5401116140321223536968
b=1111111333344444444445555555 n=p=20 K=3.5401116140321223536968
b=1111111333344444444445555555 n=p=30 K=3.5401116140321223536968
b=1111111333344444444445555555 n=p=40 K=3.5401116140321223536968
b=1111111333344444444445555555 n=p=50 K=3.5401116140321223536968

```

```

b=1111111333344444444445555555 n=p=1000 K=3.5401116140321223536
b=1111111333344444444445555555 n=p=2000 K=3.5401116140321223536
b=1111111333344444444445555555 n=p=3000 K=3.5401116140321223536
b=1111111333344444444445555555 n=p=4000 K=3.5401116140321223536
b=1111111333344444444445555555 n=p=5000 K=3.5401116140321223536

```

8. A function to calculate the (α) angle.

I point out that this is a first hypothesis, that does not provide exact results, but values that approximate them. Derives by three convincement, based on the observation of many results obtained.

- The value of (α) results, most likely, in function of the only value of (b).
- As the value of (b) increases, the value of (α) clearly tends to $\pi/4$.
- The natural logarithm is always present, in functions relating to orientations.

I would like to remind you that it is possible to precisely calculate, the orientation of the symmetry axis and from this derive the value of (α). The condition to achieve this is that $b \geq 20$ and such that the last origin of the trace, does not correspond to the origin of the complex plane.

This is the function, the result is obviously in radians.

$$\alpha(b) = \frac{\pi}{4} - \log\left(1 + \frac{1}{b}\right) \quad (14)$$

I decided to present it in what can be used, to quickly obtain, an approximate value of (α). By comparing the results obtained in the two ways, everyone will be able to decide if it makes sense to use it and for what values of (b).

Here is the confrontation, of some results (labeled AlphaB) obtained graphically, using the method mentioned above, with the results provided by function (14) and transformed into decimal degrees.

b=20 AlphaB=42.90882274° $\alpha(b)$ =42.20452951°	b=2000 AlphaB=44.9444677° $\alpha(b)$ =44.97135927°	b=2000000 AlphaB=44.99999148° $\alpha(b)$ =44.99997135°
b=100 AlphaB=44.89564617° $\alpha(b)$ =44.42988804°	b=20000 AlphaB=44.99932793° $\alpha(b)$ =44.99713528°	b=200000000 AlphaB=44.99999916° $\alpha(b)$ =44.99999971°
b=200 AlphaB=44.82710247° $\alpha(b)$ =44.71423492°	b=200000 AlphaB=44.99998717° $\alpha(b)$ =44.99971352°	b=2000000000 AlphaB=44.99999998° $\alpha(b)$ =44.99999997°

9. For what reason, if $a=1/2$, the value of (b) is neutral as regards the distance, between the two origins of the pseudo-clothoids.

Note: In this section I refer exclusively, to the traces resulting from formulation (1).

In section (6.1), I presented function (9) with which it is possible to calculate, the distance $r(p)$ between the two origins of a pseudo-clothoid, which is in position (p) , provided that $a=1/2$. Below I have provided some command lines for PARI-GP, usable for the same purpose, in cases where $a \neq 1/2$.

In this section I propose function (15), with which it is possible to calculate, for any value of (a) expressed in fractional form, the distance $r(p)$ between the two origins of a pseudo-clothoid.

Function (15) can therefore be used as a replacement for both function (9) and command lines.

As for function (4), in function (15) (nr) is the numerator of (a) and (dr) is the denominator.

$$r(p) = \frac{\sqrt{\frac{b}{2 \cdot \pi}}}{p \cdot \sqrt[dr]{\left(\frac{b}{2 \cdot \pi \cdot p}\right)^{nr}}} \quad (15)$$

For the purpose of this section and of the Riemann hypothesis, the importance of function (15) consists in the fact that, when $a=1/2$, the function simplifies itself becoming function (9), that I remember being $r(p) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{p}}$

I remember that function (4), allows you to calculate the length of single vectors. It is important to note that, when $a=1/2$, also function (4) simplifies becoming $\rho(n) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{n}}$

For $a=1/2$ (placing $p=n$) from the two functions in question, results that $\frac{1}{\sqrt{p}} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{n}}$ and therefore $r(p)=\rho(n)$.

Summarizing.

- When $a \neq 1/2$, function (15) remains unchanged; I note the presence of (b) , with all that follows.
- When $a=1/2$, function (15) simplifies itself becoming function (9), with all that follows.

What function (15) does, is calculate the length of a central part of the pseudo-clothoid, which corresponds to the distance between the two origins. It can be, considered an improved version of the command lines, which I referred to in the first part of this section.

10. Method to locate the origin of the last divergent polygonal spiral, belonging to a trace resulting from the formulation (1).

The method consists in defining two points, which together with two vertices of the trace resulting from formulation (1), for $a=1/2$ and $b \neq 0$, identify two straight line which intersect very close to the origin, of the divergent polygonal spiral, that concludes the trace.

The precision of the result is not influenced by the value of (b), but by the position of the vertices in the trace and therefore by the relative values of (n). The more $n > b/\pi$ the more precise is the result.

With the help of the scheme SCH. 2, I describe how to graphically define the two points (F) and (G) and therefore the two straight lines ($r1$) and ($r2$).

In SCH. 2 the scheme is built on the Cartesian plane, the points A, B, C, D, E, correspond in this plane to the vertices of the trace on the complex plane, of which I intend to approximate the origin. The vertices must belong to four consecutive vectors and they can be used in both the directions.

The point (F) is obtained by copying the segment (B, C) in parallel, making the copy of point (B) coincide with point (A).

The point (G) is obtained by copying the segment (D, E) in parallel, making the copy of point (D) coincide with point (C). The straight line ($r1$) identified by points (B) and (F) crosses at (OR) the straight line ($r2$), identified by points (D) and (G).

The scheme SCH. 3 depicts a similar method (it differs only in one additional step), that I created to find the origin of a logarithmic polygonal spiral, with constant angular step.

To define the points (F) and (G) in SCH. 3, after copying the segment (B, C) and the segment (D, E) they must be mirrored, using the axes of the segment (A, B) and of the segment (C, D) respectively. In this case the point (OR) always coincides with the origin, of the logarithmic polygonal spiral with constant angular step, the distance from the origin of the segments used has no influence.

The scheme SCH. 4 wants to show that in the case of a regular polygon, with a number of sides other than four, both methods work. If there are four sides, the diagonals are part of the straight lines ($r1$) and ($r2$).

I think it is time to show some examples of the latest divergent spirals.

I believe that the one hundred segments used, are sufficient, to provide a valid indication of the spirals in question.

In Fig. 17, on the left I have grouped the first hundred segments of eleven spirals, for which $a=1/2$ and $b=0.01 \div 1$. The origins, are indicated by, small circles.

In the center, enlarged ten times, the first hundred segments of the last divergent spiral, resulting from $a=1/2$ and $b=14.1347...$

On the right, enlarged two hundred times, one hundred segments of the last divergent spiral, resulting from $a=1/2$ and $b=1001.3494...$ As (f1) and (f2) indicate, in this case we are not talking about the first hundred segments, they start from $b/\pi+1000$.

Below I present some command lines that can be used with PARI-GP, to obtain the crossing point (OR) of the straight lines (r1) and (r2). These command lines, are dedicated to the traces resulting from the formulation (1), for $a=1/2$ and $b>0$. The requested data are the value of (b) and (f), the latter is the value of (n) corresponding to the starting point, of the first of the four necessary vectors.

```
Z(f,s)=sum(n=1,f,1/n^s)
b=
f=
a=1/2; s=a+b*I; fb1=f-2; fb2=f-1; Base=Z(fb1,s); Z(f,s)=Base+sum(n=fb2,f,1/n^s)
ZA=Z(f,s); xA=real(ZA); yA=imag(ZA); f=f+1; ZB=Z(f,s); xB=real(ZB); yB=imag(ZB)
f=f+1; ZC=Z(f,s); xC=real(ZC); yC=imag(ZC); f=f+1; ZD=Z(f,s); xD=real(ZD)
yD=imag(ZD); f=f+1; ZE=Z(f,s); xE=real(ZE); yE=imag(ZE)
xF=xC-xB+xA; yF=yC-yB+yA; xG=xE-xD+xC; yG=yE-yD+yC
\\----r1----
x1=xB; y1=yB; x2=xF; y2=yF; m1=(y1-y2)/(x1-x2); n1=y1-m1*x1
\\----r2----
x1=xD; y1=yD; x2=xG; y2=yG; m2=(y1-y2)/(x1-x2); n2=y1-m2*x1
\\-----
x=(n2-n1)/(m1-m2); y=m1*x+n1; OR=x+y*I
\\-----
Z=zeta(s); print("\nDIST=", sqrt((real(OR)-real(Z))^2+(imag(OR)-imag(Z))^2))
```

Note: In the rare case in which (r1) or (r2) are vertical, PARI-GP signals an error, to resolve it just change the value of (f) even slightly.

The command lines also serve to show, that the method works. Due to the zeta(s) function of PARI-GP, with a normal p.c. the last command line can be used for (b) values less than 10.000.000. In any case they are not needed, if (b) corresponds to one of those values, known as zero of the Riemann zeta function.

To approximate with (OR) the last origin of the trace, it is necessary that (f) is greater than b/π . From the tests carried out it appears that, more and more bigger is (f) respect to b/π , more greater is the precision.

Anyone interested in understanding, how I came to define this method, can find help in the following preprint, which I published on zenodo.org.

Three particular polygonal and their origins.

<http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10137173>

Some examples follow, of how the precision increases as the value of (f) increases, but also show what precision I arrived, at with my checks. The only things, that limited the degree of precision achieved, were the power of my computer and the time I was willing to wait for the results.

Note: As (n) increases, the length $\rho(n)$ of the vectors becomes, increasingly shorter. When the polygonal spiral is particularly open, it may be necessary to increase the calculation precision. In my tests, in some cases I compared, the results obtained with the default precision of PARI-GP, with the results obtained with $\backslash p 50$ (57 significant digits) and with $\backslash p 100$ (115 significant digits).

Highlighting that in the last command line, with (DIST) the comparison, between the result provided by (OR) and the result provided by the zeta(s) function of PARI-GP, is obtained, here are some of the values obtained.

f=10000000 (seven zero)	f=1000000000 (nine zero) (\p 50)
b=0.01 --> DIST=1.57... E-11	b=0.01 --> DIST=1.58... E-14
b=0.1 --> DIST=1.56... E-11	b=0.1 --> DIST=1.55... E-14
b=0.2 --> DIST=1.48... E-11	b=0.2 --> DIST=1.48... E-14
b=0.3 --> DIST=1.38... E-11	b=0.3 --> DIST=1.38... E-14
b=0.4 --> DIST=1.28... E-11	b=0.4 --> DIST=1.28... E-14
b=0.5 --> DIST=1.18... E-11	b=0.5 --> DIST=1.18... E-14
b=0.6 --> DIST=1.09... E-11	b=0.6 --> DIST=1.09... E-14
b=0.7 --> DIST=1.01... E-11	b=0.7 --> DIST=1.01... E-14
b=0.8 --> DIST=9.50... E-12	b=0.8 --> DIST=9.50... E-15
b=0.9 --> DIST=8.96... E-12	b=0.9 --> DIST=8.95... E-15
b=1.0 --> DIST=8.50... E-12	b=1.0 --> DIST=8.50... E-15

(OR) values obtained with (b) values, known as zero of the Riemann zeta function.

f=100000000 (eight zero)	f=1000000000 (nine zero) (\p 100)
b=14.13472514173469379045725198	b=14.13472514173469379045725198
OR= -1.51... E-13 - 0.73... E-13*I	OR= -4.12... E-15 + 3.33... E-15*I
-----	-----
f=2000000000 (nine zero) (\p 100)	f=4000000000 (nine zero) (\p 50)
b=14.13472514173469379045725198	b=14.13472514173469379045725198
OR= 9.29... E-16 - 1.63... E-15*I	OR= -9.65... E-17 + 6.55... E-16*I
-----	-----
f=4000000000 (nine zero) (\p 50)	f=4000000000 (nine zero) (\p 50)
b=10000.06534541453531475023...	b=1500000.612817757350274114...
OR= -2.51... E-16 + 6.09... E-16*I	OR= 3.85... E-16 + 5.35... E-16*I
-----	-----
f=1000000000 (nine zero) (\p 100)	f=2000000000 (nine zero)
b=2000000000.333438278595189...	b=2000000000.333438278595189...
OR= -6.44... E-15 - 1.62... E-14*I	OR= -2.98... E-15 + 2.22... E-15*I

f=4000000000 (nine zero)	
b=2000000000.333438278595189...	
OR= -6.40... E-16 + 4.20... E-16*I	

11. For what reasons is Riemann hypothesis true, for the traces resulting from formulation (3).

In section (13), I describe the consequences that part $(-1)^n$ has on pseudo-clothoids.

The last origins of the traces resulting from this formulation, coincide with the last origins of the traces resulting from the other two formulations, when they coincide with the origin of the complex plane.

The Riemann hypothesis concerns “non-obvious” zero, consequently also what is valid for the formulation (3), is valid for the Riemann hypothesis.

In the traces resulting from formulation (3), there is never a symmetry between the two parts of the trace. **Only for $a=1/2$ is there a compensation, between the two parties of the trace.**

SCH. 5 wants to schematically show that there can be no symmetry, in the traces resulting from formulation (3), but on condition that $a=1/2$, there can be compensation.

Also in the trace resulting from formulation (3), the hinge vector is present, to delimit the two parts of the trace. Unlike the traces resulting from formulation (1), in this case there is no relationship, between the symmetry axis and the hinge vector, when $a=1/2$. The symmetry axis can only randomly cross the hinge vector.

Differences regarding the Riemann hypothesis, of the traces resulting from formulation (3), respect to the traces resulting from formulation (1).

- The correspondences between pseudo-clothoids and vectors present in the first part of the trace, involve only the vectors that correspond to odd (n) values. This means that, the last pseudo-clothoid has correspondence with the first vector, the penultimate with the third, the third to last with the fifth, ...
- Given $a=1/2$, the distance between the two origins of a pseudo-clothoid, is always greater, than the length of the corresponding vector.

Equalities regarding the Riemann hypothesis, of the traces resulting from formulation (3), respect to the traces resulting from formulation (1).

- For any value of (s) in which $b > \pi$, there is always symmetry of orientations between pseudo-clothoids and corresponding vectors, in the first part of the trace.
- Neutrality of the value of (b), with respect to the distance between the two origins of the pseudo-clothoids, on condition that is $a=1/2$. There is no equality but, if $a=1/2$, the ratio between distances and lengths remains fixed, does not depend on the value of (b) and does not depend on the position of the pseudo-clothoid in the trace.
- When $a \neq 1/2$, the value of (b) affects the distance between the two origins of the pseudo-clothoids, in the same way as already described for formulation (1).

In the next section, I present some functions, valid for the traces resulting from formulation (3).

12. Graphic analysis of the traces resulting from the formulation (3).

Fig. 18 uses a trace resulting from formulation (3), which presents a situation similar to the traces inserted in Fig. 3 and Fig. 4.

In this case I use the trace to highlight, the correspondence of the pseudo-clothoids, with the vectors of the first part of the trace, resulting from (n) odd.

Being $a=1/2$, I also highlight the relationship that binds the distances between two origins of the pseudo-clothoids, to the lengths of the corresponding vectors, in the first part of the trace.

The following descriptions concern the traces indicated, by the five references shown in the image.

- (1) This is the complete trace, I used two colors to distinguish the two parts.
- (2) Highlighted in green the vectors of the first part of the trace, corresponding to (n) odd.
- (3) Group the highlighted vectors and indicate the length of the first vector, for which $n=1$.
- (4) Mirrored with respect to the axis of symmetry the trace obtained in (3) and enlarged by $1/\sqrt{0.5}$.
- (5) Superposition of the trace obtained in (4) on the trace (1).

$1/\sqrt{0.5}$ is the constant ratio, existing between the distances of the two origins of the pseudo-clothoids and the lengths of the corresponding vectors, in the first part of the trace, for $b \geq \pi$ provided that is $a=1/2$.

Note: for the traces represented in Fig. 18÷21, the points resulting from $n=1 \div 5000$ were used.

- Three functions that allow to calculate, for a given pseudo-clothoid, the values of (n) corresponding to the first, last and intermediate vector. Valid for formulation (3).

The value of (n) corresponds to the end point of the vector, (p) is the position of the pseudo-clothoid, p=1 corresponds to the last pseudo-clothoid.

Last vector (rounding to the previous integer)
$$n(p) = \frac{b}{\pi \cdot (2 \cdot p - 2)} \quad (16)$$

Point (M_p) (rounding to the nearest integer)
$$n(p) = \frac{b}{\pi \cdot (2 \cdot p - 1)} \quad (17)$$

First vector (rounding to the next integer)
$$n(p) = \frac{b}{2 \cdot \pi \cdot p} \quad (18)$$

I note that for the function (16), the minimum value of (p) can only be 2.

From functions (16), (17) and (18) it is clear that the divisor of (b), for p=1 is: 0, π, 2π, for p=2 is 2π, 3π, 4π, and so on (as long as the increase of (p) is useful).

- Command lines for PARI-GP, useful for identifying the origins of pseudo-clothoids, in the traces resulting from formulation (3).

```
a=
b=
p=
s=a+b*I
x1=b/(Pi*(2*p-2))
x2=truncate(b/(Pi*(2*p-2)))
Z(f,s)=sum(n=1,f,(-1)^n*n^(-s))
if((x1-x2) < 0.5, f1=truncate(b/(Pi*(2*p-2)))-1, f1=truncate(b/(Pi*(2*p-2))))
f2=f1+1
z1=Z(f1,s)
z2=Z(f2,s)
Cp=(real(z1)+real(z2))/2+((imag(z1)+imag(z2))/2)*I
```

The requested data are (a), (b) and (p).

The difference between (x1) and (x2) determines which of the two vectors, has its midpoint closest to the origin.

(z1) and (z2) are the extremes of the vector used and (C_p) is the midpoint, which we assume as the origin C_p=D_{p-1}.

Note: These command lines use function (16), for this function, the minimum value of (p) can only be 2.

The custom function Z(f,s), has the drawback of starting over from 1, at each increase in the value of (n). For values of (b) which involve long times, I use the following command line variant.

I somehow solved the problem, by calculating a value (Base) just smaller than (z1).

```

a=
b=
p=
s=a+b*I
x1=b/(Pi*(2*p-2))
x2=truncate(b/(Pi*(2*p-2)))
Z(f,s)=sum(n=1,f,(-1)^n*n^(-s))
if((x1-x2) < 0.5, f1=truncate(b/(Pi*(2*p-2)))-1, f1=truncate(b/(Pi*(2*p-2))))
f2=f1+1
fb1=f1-2
fb2=f1-1
Base=Z(fb1,s)
Z(f,s)=Base+sum(n=fb2,f,(-1)^n*n^(-s))
z1=Z(f1,s)
z2=Z(f2,s)
Cp=(real(z1)+real(z2))/2+((imag(z1)+imag(z2))/2)*I

```

- Distance between the two origins of a pseudo-clothoid. Function valid for formulation (3).

This function, for the traces resulting from formulation (3) and only if $a=1/2$, allows to calculate the distance between the two origins of a pseudo-clothoid.

$$r(p) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{p - 0.5}} \quad (19)$$

It is clear that it is derived from function (9).

Also for this function I point out that only the square root is required.

The difference compared to function (9), is a consequence of the presence of $(-1)^n$ in formulation (3).

In another way it is possible to calculate $r(p)$ when $a \neq 1/2$. In this case I use the following command lines for PARI-GP.

With these command lines, starting from the resulting value of $r(p)$ for $a=1/2$, the distance between the two origins of the pseudo-clothoid is obtained, given the values of (b) , (p) and $a \neq 1/2$.

```

b=
p=
nr=
dr=
medio=b/(Pi*(2*p-1))  \\ In this case, rounding would be counterproductive.
rBase=1/sqrt(p-0.5)
rho1=1/sqrt(medio)
rho2=1/sqrtn(medio^nr,dr)
rpb=(rho2/rho1)*rBase

```

As for function (4), (nr) and (dr) used in the penultimate line, are the numerator and denominator of (a) , expressed in fractional form.

- Inclination of the axis of symmetry.

When the value of (b) is large enough, I use the following command lines for PARI-GP, with which I calculate (in decimal degrees), the inclination of the symmetry axis, which I call Gamma. As for the vectors, the zero is at 3.00 and for (b) positive the increase is clockwise.

```

b=
p=1
n(p)=round(b/(Pi*(2*p-1)))
if(type(n(p)/2) == "t_INT", ThetaM(p)=b*log(n(p)), ThetaM(p)=b*log(n(p))+Pi)
ThetaMp=ThetaM(p)*180/Pi-(truncate((ThetaM(p)*180/Pi)/360)*360)
Beta=ThetaMp-45
Gamma=Beta/2 \\ It can even be Gamma=180+Beta/2

```

Once n(p) has been calculated, it is checked whether it is even or odd, if it is odd π is added to ThetaM(p).

As data only (b) is required, in these command lines n(p) has the same role, that in function (5) it is played by (n), n(p) is calculated using function (17).

The ThetaMp angle is obtained by transforming ThetaM(p) into decimal degrees and removing the multiples of 360°.

12.1 Verification of the method of calculating the origins of pseudo-clothoids.

Fig. 19 represents the trace resulting from formulation (3) by $s=1/2+ 10002.279122...i$. Also in this case I highlighted, with two different colors, the two parts of the trace.

As for Fig. 18 I reconstructed the trace, which highlights the origins of the pseudo-clothoid and inserted it into the image.

I wanted to highlight, some of the symmetrical orientations with respect to the axis and also the different functions that determine the length of the vectors, in the first part of the trace and the distances between the two origins of the pseudo-clothoids.

With reference to the trace inserted in Fig. 19, I calculated the values (Z_n) of the final points of the first five vectors and using function (16), I calculated the three origins preceding the last one.

I also computed the length of the first three vectors resulting from (n) odd and the distance between the two origins of the last three pseudo-clothoids.

These are the results I got.

$Z_1 = -1 + 0 \cdot i$
 $Z_2 = -1.638724157877032606167335525884601 - 0.303366857359658730007494912727300 \cdot i$
 $Z_3 = -2.093284440986123294399889252042196 - 0.659327925951599913501934545108223 \cdot i$
 $Z_4 = -1.777347341274674346718539328653685 - 0.271792444961900126168607305758435 \cdot i$
 $Z_5 = -2.164001349446660200341300255095067 - 0.047073335929005692335089485278568 \cdot i$
 $D_1 = C_2 = -1.283162478503406843781152916755053 + 0.594556968627555127166520118727396 \cdot i$
 $D_2 = C_3 = -1.654785848808623061580695234990198 + 1.321578166523281281005006737120029 \cdot i$
 $D_3 = C_4 = -2.284433631438870183495726844887566 + 1.263025292562462570056200925044291 \cdot i$
 $\rho_1 = 1$
 $\rho_3 = 0.57735026918962576450914878050195745565$
 $\rho_5 = 0.44721359549995793928183473374625524709$
 $r_1 = 1.4142135623730950488016887242096980786$
 $r_2 = 0.81649658092772603273242802490196379732$
 $r_3 = 0.63245553203367586639977870888654370674$

- What changes if $a \neq 1/2$.

Fig. 20 represents the trace resulting from formulation (3) by $s = 4/9 + 10002.279122...i$. Also in this case I highlighted, with two different colors, the two parts of the trace.

To the calculations I added the one relating to the second origin, of the last pseudo-clothoid (point of convergence), to obtain it I multiplied by $(2^{(1-s)} - 1)$, the result provided by the zeta(s) function for $s = 4/9 + 10002.279122...i$.

Note: In Fig. 20 and Fig. 21 I chose to position the axis of symmetry, so that it crosses the same cross vector in Fig. 19.

Fig. 20

These are the results I got.

$Z1=-1 + 0*i$
 $Z2=-1.663799973963125858126022526681501 - 0.315276805383311567469441768290385*i$
 $Z3=-2.146968040495755960440727618067216 - 0.693640308890680710407162424890606*i$
 $Z4=-1.805737099075015911043347861295250 - 0.275078838481441276669490272820530*i$
 $Z5=-2.228555796030617473607418017273823 - 0.029341205212038361999818404457253*i$
 $D1=C2=-0.844083849214680311506142120441731 + 0.676134190150448843503745369410517*i$
 $D2=C3=-1.391358299718636996827306422715199 + 1.746785740254580445415333285380857*i$
 $D3=C4=-2.292670854762170219010821718084008 + 1.662970865527880009782014453082162*i$
 $\rho1=1$
 $\rho3=0.61368584903291603508168767420564100200$
 $\rho5=0.48904256961953771033394713081192870859$
 $r1b=2.2137230189003707100535479809979535230$
 $r2b=1.2024192412610305484757424099534070630$
 $r3b=0.90532937475058220152542575646836098340$
 $s=4/9+10002.2791222728886154882113785932532*i$
 $zeta(s)*(2^{(1-s)}-1)$
 $=1.164499829170593077276209230698447 - 0.254548879893486524595917644381790*i$

Fig. 21 represents the trace resulting from formulation (3) by $s=5/9+ 10002.279122...i$. Also in this case I highlighted, with two different colors, the two parts of the trace.

These are the results I got.

$Z1 = -1 + 0 \cdot i$
 $Z2 = -1.614595609909420031938113078988223 - 0.291906821475129655873893367877922 \cdot i$
 $Z3 = -2.042241941056725963637895051453919 - 0.626791875605750476331881614900806 \cdot i$
 $Z4 = -1.749723769760507181122934710491636 - 0.267982573643295476102598802745711 \cdot i$
 $Z5 = -2.103306340994722533104023465398917 - 0.062484224478452488864569326243985 \cdot i$
 $D1=C2 = -1.568419919230917133031524691201403 + 0.486414295981613832042610445277910 \cdot i$
 $D2=C3 = -1.820768641064810694857562088294436 + 0.980094751504991255497370052178470 \cdot i$
 $D3=C4 = -2.260634141136405031395160523517559 + 0.939189730242510017194192338930570 \cdot i$
 $\rho1 = 1$
 $\rho3 = 0.54316607407294877966782901238146633121$
 $\rho5 = 0.40896235302295821244831773986522580160$
 $r1b = 0.90345539298474025548422164203563630405$
 $r2b = 0.55443778990720713714153709901370795626$
 $r3b = 0.44182814692188663789834246991783309753$
 $s = 5/9 + 10002.2791222728886154882113785932532 \cdot i$
 $zeta(s) \cdot (2^{1-s} - 1)$
 $= -0.748684995641149985675167488261507 + 0.106588173224684638881931545856579 \cdot i$

13. Consequences of part $(-1)^n$ on the traces of the Riemann zeta function, resulting from formulations (2) and (3).

Part $(-1)^n$ reverses the direction of the vectors, corresponding to (n) odd, which means one vector in every pair of vectors that follow each other.

The first effect is found with the first vector, of the traces resulting from formulation (3), which terminates for any value of (s) in $-1 + 0i$. I remember that the first vector, in the traces resulting from the formulation (1), ends for any value of (s) in $1 + 0i$.

It is necessary to analyze the final part of the traces, to understand the effect that the $(-1)^n$ part has on the pseudo-clothoids and in which way convergence is possible.

I repeat Fig. 5, remembering that it is extracted from a trace resulting from formulation (1), in which it is not present the $(-1)^n$ part. I use it to remember a characteristic of pseudo-clothoids.

It can be observed that in correspondence of the two origins, the following vector tends to reverse the direction of previous vector. As the comparison with Figs. 6 and 7 also shows, this is happening more and more evident, approaching the last pseudo-clothoid and with increasing value of (b) .

In the same image, it can be seen that in the central part of the pseudo-clothoids, the next vector tends to keep the same direction as the previous vector. This too is happening more and more clearly approaching the last pseudo-clothoid and with increasing value of (b) .

It appears evident that, in the traces resulting from formulation (3), the inversion of one vector every two transforms, the origins of the pseudo-clothoids in the central parts and the central parts in the origins.

- Consequences of part $(-1)^n$ analyzed using the $\theta(n)$ curve, having as reference the results produced by formulation (1).

As a basis for the analysis, I use three characteristics, that can be found in the traces resulting from formulation (3).

- Phase shift equal to half a pseudo-clothoid.
- As a consequence of the growth mode of the $\theta(n)$ curve, an increase in the number of vectors forming the last pseudo-clothoids.
- The second part of the last pseudo-clothoid, exceeds the section of the $\theta(n)$ curve, in which the pseudo-clothoids are formed.

In Diag. 2 I reported on the $\theta(n)$ curve, the positions corresponding to the origins of the pseudo-clothoids, resulting from the same value of (s). On the first curve those of the trace resulting from formulation (1), on the second curve those of the trace resulting from formulation (3). Diag. 2 is also rotated 90° clockwise to take up less space.

In the same diagram I highlighted, by connecting them with a dashed line, the positions corresponding to the origins, from which the last pseudo-clothoids begin. I then highlighted that the same value of (n), for formulation (1) corresponds to the last origin of the trace, while, for formulation (3) corresponds to point (M) of the last pseudo-clothoid.

The same conclusion is reached, by comparing functions (16), (17) and (18) with functions (6), (7) and (8).

In Diag. 2 we note that for formulation (3), the origin from which the last pseudo-clothoid begins, is found in a more advanced position on the $\theta(n)$ curve, compared to the corresponding one resulting from formulation (1). From point (M) begins for all pseudo-clothoids, the convergence towards the second origin. The growth mode of the $\theta(n)$ curve, makes at this point the convergence irreversible, for the traces resulting from formulation (3).

14. Graphical analysis of the traces resulting from the Riemann's version, of the Euler's product.

Note: In this section, (p) has a completely different meaning, from what it has in the other sections.

The zeta function, object of this manuscript, is the second part of the Riemann's version, of the equality already proposed by Euler.

$$\prod \frac{1}{1 - \frac{1}{p^s}} = \sum \frac{1}{n^s}$$

In the Euler version, (p) are prime numbers while (n) and (s) are natural numbers.

The innovation introduced by Riemann, was to use for (s) the complex numbers.

In doing this, Riemann hypothesized that the "non-obvious" zero resulting from the second part of the equality, are complex numbers with the real part 1/2.

Obviously, the same must also apply to the first part of the equality.

The traces object of this section, highlight the following characteristics.

- As for the traces resulting from the formulation (1), show that they are not convergent for $a=1/2$.
- After an initial part, similar to the initial part of the traces resulting from formulation (1), they draw increasingly larger circular traces.
- Given the same (s), they tend to position themselves on the plane, having as reference, a point corresponding to the last origin (Of), of the traces resulting from formulation (1).
- The final form to which they tend, results influenced by the origin of the complex plane. This also happens when, (Of) coincides with the origin of the plane.

As for the traces resulting from formulation (1), also the trace resulting from the first part of the equality, highlight for $a=1/2$, the lack of final convergence. In the presence of non-converging traces, it seems clear to me, that the equality can only concern, the last origins (Of).

To confirm the highlighted points, I present below some images of the traces.

To obtain the traces in question, I created a custom function for PARI-GP, the basis is the function `prodeuler(p=a,b,expr)`.

```
Z(p,s)=prodeuler(p=1,p+1,1/(1-(1/p^s)))
```

Based on this custom function, I created three series of command lines for PARI-GP.

The first series is useful when you want to obtain traces, that start correctly from the origin of the complex plane, the data requested are (a), (b) and (f), the latter determines the end of the trace.

```
Z(p,s)=prodeuler(p=1,p+1,1/(1-(1/p^s)))
```

```
a=
```

```
b=
```

```
s=a+b*I
```

```
f=
```

```
for(p=1,2, if(p/2 > truncate(p/2), print("0,0 " real(Z(p,s)) ", " imag(Z(p,s))))
```

```
for(p=3,f, if(isprime(p), print(real(Z(p,s)) ", " imag(Z(p,s))))
```

The second series is useful when you want to obtain, only those parts of the trace that interest you, the data requested are (a), (b), (f1) and (f2).

```
Z(p,s)=prodeuler(p=1,p+1,1/(1-(1/p^s)))
a=
b=
s=a+b*I
f1=
f2=
for(p=f1,f2, if(isprime(p), print(real(Z(p,s)) ", " imag(Z(p,s)))))
```

The third series produces the same result as the previous one, it is useful for reducing execution times, when it is necessary to use (f1) and (f2) values that are starting to be challenging.

```
Z(p,s)=prodeuler(p=1,p+1,1/(1-(1/p^s)))
a=
b=
s=a+b*I
f1=
f2=
fb1=f1-2
fb2=f1-1
Base=Z(fb1,s)
Z(p,s)=Base*prodeuler(p=fb2,p+1,1/(1-(1/p^s)))
for(p=f1,f2, if(isprime(p), print(real(Z(p,s)) ", " imag(Z(p,s)))))
```

In the images, the axes corresponding to the origin of the plane are black, the axes corresponding to point (Of) are yellow.

Fig. 22 provides a first example, of what was previous described.

The final values of (p) shown in the image, are intended to show that as the value of (b) increases, a greater number of vectors are needed to reach similar situations.

Fig. 23 presents the initial part of the trace at the bottom left, in this first part it seems that the trace converges on (Of), in reality it is only a first positioning.

In the same image I repositioned the axes and reported subsequent parts of the same trace, the choice to fragment the trace is due to the enormous number of vectors necessary, but also to the desire to show how the trace evolves, avoiding overlaps that would make the image less readable.

Even in this case you can notice the tendency towards better positioning, of the trace with respect to (Of) and the influence of the origin of the complex plane, on the path of the trace.

The trace inserted in Fig. 24 derives from a value of (b) chosen so that, (Of) is further away from the origin of the complex plane, than the trace in Fig. 23. In addition to the initial part I inserted subsequent parts of the same trace, colored in yellow. I hope the correspondence with Fig. 23 is evident.

For Fig. 25 I chose a value of (b), known to be the first zero of the Riemann zeta function. The point (Of) coincides with the origin of the complex plane.

On the left the initial part of the trace is enlarged five times, in the center a detail of the trace near the origin and on the right the resulting trace up to the value of (p) indicated.

The limited value of (p) seems to have been sufficient to position the trace, in such a way that it appears quite correct with respect to point (Of).

However, I would like to point out that the initial part of the trace is composed, of a number of vectors more than six times that of the trace inserted in Fig. 22, resulting from a comparable (b) value.

I cannot say whether it is due to the coincidence of (Of) with the origin of the plane, or to the relationship between the number of vectors that compose it and the value of (b), in fact I think it is the most beautiful trace of this section.

I think it is important to note that this is the initial part, of an infinitely larger trace.

A. Use of Use of Computer Aided Design.

This appendix is dedicated to those who would be interested, in analyze with the CAD the traces in question, but are held back by the fact of not knowing what characteristics the CAD must have and above all how get PARI-GP, results formatted to be rows of CAD command.

To obtain the necessary results, to report the traces in the CAD issue I use PARI-GP, which I recommend. You can download it free, easy to install and use, it is fast, powerful, flexible...

PARI-GP, can be downloaded from the website <https://pari.math.u-bordeaux.fr>

In fact CAD doesn't require many hints, I think they will turn out the suggestions I provide on the use of PARI-GP, are more useful for many.

The examples that I present in this appendix, concern only traces resulting from formulation (1).

A.1. Characteristics that the CAD must have.

- You don't need a 3D CAD, the traces in question develop on a plane two-dimensional, which should be the complex plane. I remember that though the complex plane was derived from the Cartesian plane, assuming that the (y) axis was the imaginary axis and the (x) axis was the real axis.
- It must have a command line that can accept that, an unlimited number of text strings are pasted, or must accept commands via scripts.
- It must allow you to work on the four quadrants of the Cartesian plane.
- Regarding the number of decimals, that can be set for the plus odds the more the better, but this is a surmountable problem.

A.2. PARI-GP functions and commands, useful for obtaining the data needed by the CAD.

The following command lines for PARI-GP, get the values of $Z(f,s)$, for (n) from (f1) to (f2). As data requires (a), (b), (f1) and (f2).

It can be seen that the last line transforms the coordinates for the complex plane, into coordinates for the Cartesian plane.

```
Z(f,s)=sum(n=1,f,1/n^s)
a=
b=
s=a+b*I
f1=
f2=
for(f=f1,f2, print(real(Z(f,s)) ", " imag(Z(f,s))))
```

The custom function that does the calculations, to get the points relative to the vertices of the trace, has the drawback of starting over from $n=1$, for the calculation of each new point.

For large final values of (n), the waiting time can become excessively long.

-0.12414041964635508239438779885659557066,0.090534659711153741734729335601611318996
 0.066470878559482269535689113928325007782,-0.12626171094485765551344376202154909875
 -0.040202059491024795274084800416928519933,0.12975383782269201787438036944816468703
 0.045263818446785109560047871762432781861,-0.12347363923477662273598896350861675304

When there are several zero at the beginning of the part in the results decimal, PARI-GP uses scientific notation and this normally creates problems for the CAD.

If it is a question of a few cases they can be corrected manually, if they are many can use an artifice to get around the problem.

The artifice is to insert a multiplier in the last row of command. The trace will be larger depending on the multiplier.

If the accuracy of the CAD permits, the trace can then be scaled, with base on the origin, to bring it back to the correct size and position, otherwise we must limit ourselves to taking them into account.

Obviously the same multiplier, must act on both coordinates, here is an example.

```
Multiplier=1000000
for(f=f1,f2, print(real(Z(f,s))*Multiplier "," imag(Z(f,s))*Multiplier))
```

It happened to me in a few cases that, I needed to increase the default precision by PARI-GP, just in case here is how.

\p n Where (n) indicates the number of digits to display, but also acts on the calculation precision.

A.3. Checking and adapting text for CAD.

The text to be transferred to the CAD must start with the line containing the command, which can be "line" but can also be "pline" or other equivalents accepted by the CAD.

As already highlighted, CAD does not normally accept numbers in notation scientific, in conclusion the first three lines in the example case should be as follows.

```
line
0,0
1.00000000000000000000000000000000000,0
```

The first few times I think you'll want to get full traces (up to round(b/Pi)), later you may want to get only the part of relevant trace.

In the second case I recommend adding (except in particular cases), in addition to the command the second line as well, so you get a line that starts from the origin and connects to the relevant part of the trace.

The reason is to easily, locate a part of the trace that can also be very small and have a certain connection with the origin.

As for PARI-GP also the CAD can have problems with some characters, possibly modified by the text editor used to adapt the results to the CAD, if this happens you probably need to use a different text editor.

A.4. Data transfer to CAD.

First you need to be able to locate and highlight the origin of the plan.

It should be noted that CAD, allows you to draw traces with dimensions of several millimeters, the traces we want to obtain have the size of a few millimeters, but even less.

Normally, the CAD allows you to set the limits of the drawing and of adjust the initial display to the set limits.

It is advisable to set limits that delimit a window of a few millimeters and chosen so as, to have the origin in the center of the screen. The first times perhaps it is better to draw the axes of the plane.

The command followed by the coordinates of the points is a classic that should be compatible, with any CAD. With command lines, correct as I described, the CAD must therefore create the following trace.

If the CAD does not accept, that an unlimited number of text strings, it needs to accept scripts, in this case the file created by PARI-GP will probably have to have, the extension required by the CAD for script files.

If the CAD accepts scripts it must have a command that allows you, to locate the file and run the script.

For those wishing to try to make Figs. 6 and 7, perhaps further help is needed.

Here are the two sets of command lines that, allow you to get the two parts that make up, the trace represented in Fig. 6.

```
Z(f,s)=sum(n=1,f,1/n^s)
a=1/2
b=10000.0653454145353147502287213889928
s=a+b*I
f1=3083
f2=3183
for(f=f1,f2, if(f/2 > truncate(f/2), print("linea\n" real(Z(f,s)) ", " imag(Z(f,s))), print(real(Z(f,s)) ", " imag(Z(f,s)) "\n")))
```

Note: $(f/2) > \text{truncate}(f/2)$ forces the vectors starting in (n) odd to be drawn, so they end in (n) even.

```
Z(f,s)=sum(n=1,f,1/n^s)
a=1/2
b=10000.0653454145353147502287213889928
s=a+b*I
f1=3083
f2=3183
for(f=f1,f2, if(f/2 == truncate(f/2), print("linea\n" real(Z(f,s)) ", " imag(Z(f,s))), print(real(Z(f,s)) ", " imag(Z(f,s)) "\n")))
```

Note: $(f/2) == \text{truncate}(f/2)$ forces the vectors starting in (n) even to be drawn, so they end in (n) odd.

I note that in both cases, PARI-GP inserts a number in scientific notation. Remember that you must, always delete all the lines that precede the first “line” command.

Obviously, in both cases if the CAD requires a command other than “line” it is necessary to correct, the last of the command lines that I put a disposition.

Last note, in these two cases the following two lines should not be inserted at the beginning.

```
line
0,0
```

B. False pseudo-clothoids.

The following image uses twice the same part of the trace (in which the hinge vector is present) resulting from formulation (1) by $a=1/2$ and $b=11520199.281$. In the image, at the top I added the axis of symmetry and colored the two parts of the trace that I compare at the bottom, in the same image.

The red vectors are in the first part of the trace, the blue vectors are in the second part of the trace.

In both parts of the trace there are geometries, which may look like pseudo-clothoids.

I use two reasons to say that they cannot be pseudo-clothoids.

- The red vectors are in the first part of the trace.
- The blue vectors are at the beginning of the second part of the trace, where the real pseudo-clothoids are formed of only one vector.

The (graphic) confirmation that in this case the real pseudo-clothoids are formed by a single vector, is provided by the interweaving that can be observed at the bottom right, between the mirror copy of the red vectors and the blue vectors.

C. Further evidence of symmetry and confirmation of the validity of functions (6), (7) and (8).

In the following image two parts can be distinguished, the upper part is constructed by tracing the first six vectors and the axis of symmetry. The blue trace is a mirror copy of the first six vectors with respect to the axis of symmetry. As already highlighted, the blue trace corresponds to the axes of the last six pseudo-clothoids.

The value of (b) used corresponds to a zero of the Riemann zeta function. I chose a trace that was as horizontal and linear as possible, in the initial and final parts.

In the lower part I compared the blue trace with the first 43 vectors that diverge from (Of), but also with the vectors that end at point (M_p) and with the two vectors (last and first) that converge and diverge with respect to the origins that precede (Of).

Here are some of the command lines for PARI-GP used to make the previous image.

I highlight that (in the command lines) to move from one position to the next, I simply increased by 1 (in the line that performs the calculation of (f1)) the multiplier of π .

With the following lines I calculated the points relating to the first six vectors.

```
Z(f,s)=sum(n=1,f,1/n^s)
a=1/2
b=2864.9114267588514456131322137967878
s=a+b*I
f1=0
f2=6
for(f=f1,f2, print(real(Z(f,s)) ", " imag(Z(f,s))))
```

With the following lines I calculated the points relating to the first 43 vectors of the last divergent spiral with origin at point (Of).

```
Z(f,s)=sum(n=1,f,1/n^s)
a=1/2
b=2864.9114267588514456131322137967878
s=a+b*I
f1=truncate(b/Pi)
f2=f1+43
for(f=f1,f2, print(real(Z(f,s)) ", " imag(Z(f,s))))
```

With the following lines I calculated the initial and final points of the vector that ends in (M_1) .

```
Z(f,s)=sum(n=1,f,1/n^s)
a=1/2
b=2864.9114267588514456131322137967878
s=a+b*I
f1=round(b/(2*Pi))-1
f2=f1+1
for(f=f1,f2, print(real(Z(f,s)) ", " imag(Z(f,s))))
```

With the following lines I calculated the points relating to the last vector that converges on $(D_1=C_2)$ and to the first vector that diverges from the same point.

```
Z(f,s)=sum(n=1,f,1/n^s)
a=1/2
b=2864.9114267588514456131322137967878
s=a+b*I
f1=truncate(b/(3*Pi))-1
f2=f1+2
for(f=f1,f2, print(real(Z(f,s)) ", " imag(Z(f,s))))
```

As for Fig. 03, 04 and 18 it should be evident that the value of (b) has been carefully chosen.

In this case I needed a zero that was approximately 3000, but also a trace in which the first six vectors created an initial part as parallel as possible to the real axis and without crossings. I also needed an axis of symmetry as parallel as possible to the real axis.

I found the definitive value of (b) on Imfdb.org, but I found the approximate value quite quickly and effortlessly thanks to an “activity” (that’s what they call it in geogebra.org) that I created using the GeoGebra Classic 5 software.

At the moment I have not published this activity on the geogebra.org website, but I have published others with which you can see (for a limited numbers of vectors) how the traces resulting from the Riemann zeta function change when the values of (a) and (b) are modified.

This is the link to one of them.

<https://www.geogebra.org/m/bwypnxvx>

D. Two vectors to calculate the last origin (O_f) more precisely.

This section concerns the traces resulting from formulation (1). The two vectors in question are, the last vector of the last pseudo-clothoid (sky blue in Fig. D01, D02 and D03) and the first vector of the divergent spiral that concludes the trace (brown in Fig. D01, D02 and D03).

The method I describe is an evident improvement over the method presented in section (6.1), but even in this case, the achieved precision is conditioned by the values of (a) and (b) .

The higher the value of (a) , the smaller the length of the two vectors, with the same value of (b) . The higher the value of (b) , the smaller the maximum angle between the two vectors. Accuracy improves the shorter the two vectors are and the smaller the maximum angle separating them.

The method uses the functions (4), (5), (6) and (8), to calculate the lengths of the two vectors and to calculate the angle between the two vectors. The useful angle is obtained using a value of (b) such that b/π is the integer preceding the value resulting from the actual value of (b) .

Given the same integer part of the number resulting from b/π , the angle between the two vectors is max. when b/π is an integer and resets to zero when the decimal part of b/π is 0.5, then increases again.

- Position of the last origin with respect to the two vectors.

When (s) is not a non-obvious zero, I use the result of the PARI-GP zeta(s) function as a comparison. From the results of the zeta(s) function results that the last origin is between the two vectors (very close to the last) only when b/π is an integer or very close to it, in other case and if $a \neq 0$, the last origin is positioned with respect to the two vectors in a way equivalent to that represented in Fig. D01.

In the images, the pairs of vectors have an orientation that I consider useful.

The way I determine the value of (b), allows to choose the decimal part of b/π and this results useful, to note where is the origin located with respect to the vectors, as a function of the decimal part of b/π .

Fig. D02 shows the two vectors resulting from three values of (a) and from the same (b). I chose to resize the vectors using the (M) multiplier, which acts on the vectors and (only for Fig. D02 and Fig. D04) also on zeta(s) and (Of). I invite you to note the position of (Of) with respect to the midpoints of the two vectors and the dimensions (B) and (H) that define it. I used a small (b) value and a particular decimal part resulting from b/π , to improve readability.

- Description of the method.

The value of (B) is calculated by dividing the difference in length of the two vectors by 4, if $a=0$ then $B=0$. As you can see in Fig. D03, the value of (H) is calculated starting from the distance between the two vectors, at two points at a distance from the vertex that is the average of the two midpoints. The angle must be the one resulting from the (b) corresponding to the integer value of b/π , which precedes the one resulting from the actual (b). To obtain the final value of (H) the multiplier (dec) is needed, which corresponds to the decimal part of b/π if it is ≤ 0.5 , otherwise $dec=1-dec$.

Below are the PARI-GP command lines with which, given the numerator (nr) and the denominator (dr) of (a) and given (b) you get (Of). If you want, you can get the (DIST) comparison with zeta(s), to get the comparison you need to remove the two backslashes, at the beginning of the last two command lines. The command lines are intended for large values of (b), see section (6.1), for $b < 2.5 * \pi$ you get errors. In case it was necessary, I have foreseen the multiplier (M) to which I have assigned the value 1.

You can notice that in (SPT) the real part is (B) and the imaginary part is (H).

The command lines also allow negative (a) values, although for $a < 0$ the precision worsens, in proportion to the length of the two vectors.

```
nr=
dr=
b=
M=1
a=nr/dr
s=a+b*I
Z(f,s)=sum(n=1,f,1/n^s)
n=truncate(b/Pi)
Tu=b*log(n); NTu=Tu-(truncate((Tu)/(2*Pi))*2*Pi); if(NTu > Pi, NTu=NTu-Pi)
Tp=b*log(n+1); NTP=TP-(truncate((TP)/(2*Pi))*2*Pi); if(NTP > Pi, NTP=NTP-Pi)
VS=NTP-NTu
if(VS < 0, f1=truncate(b/Pi)-1, f1=truncate(b/Pi))
f2=f1+1
fb1=f1-2
fb2=f1-1
Base=Z(fb1,s)
Z(f,s)=Base+sum(n=fb2,f,1/n^s)
z1=Z(f1,s)
z2=Z(f2,s)
PM=(real(z1)+real(z2))/2+((imag(z1)+imag(z2))/2)*I
\\ Calculation of (H)
b0=truncate(b/Pi)*Pi
dec=b/Pi-truncate(b/Pi)
if(dec > 0.5, dec=1-dec)
if(VS < 0, dec=-1*dec)
n0=truncate(b0/Pi); L0=(1/sqrtn(n0^nr, dr)+1/sqrtn((n0+1)^nr, dr))/2.0
Tu0=b0*log(n0)
Tp0=b0*log(n0+1)
Ti0=abs(Tp0-Tu0); Ti0=Pi-Ti0-truncate(Ti0/(2*Pi))*2*Pi
H0=2*L0/2*sin(Ti0/2); H=H0*dec
\\ Calculation of (B)
Luv=1/sqrtn(n^nr, dr)
Lpv=1/sqrtn((n+1)^nr, dr)
B=abs(Luv-Lpv)/4.0
\\ Calculation of (Of)
if(VS < 0, Tv=Tu, Tv=Tp)
if(a > 0, SPT=M*B-M*H*I, SPT=M*B+M*H*I)
if(a > 0, Of=M*PM + SPT*cos(Tv)-SPT*sin(Tv)*I, Of=M*PM - SPT*cos(Tv)+SPT*sin(Tv)*I)
print("\nOf=", Of, "\n")
\\ Comparison between (Of) and zeta(s)
\\Pc=zeta(s)
\\print("\nDIST=", sqrt((real(Of)-real(Pc))^2+(imag(Of)-imag(Pc))^2), "\n")
```

Remembering that with the method presented in section (6.1), to have a precision of the order of 10^{-16} , a (b) value greater than thirty billion is required, here are some results obtained with this method.

Result obtained by $a=1/2$ and $b=10.000.000$ using the result of the zeta(s) function of PARI-GP as reference.
Of=11.458040610577092541857807791193770964 - 8.6434372268360217106943350121620138002*I
Pc=11.458040610577092545002268589041325797 - 8.6434372268360217238182148996339272448*I
DIST=1.3495327228711050583946788473782702207 E-17

With my p.c. $b=10.000.000$ is close to the limit allowed by zeta(s), here are four results obtained using non-obvious zero, for the first three I left the default precision, for the last one I used $\backslash p 100$.

Result obtained by $a=1/2$ and $b=100000000.6429256385975183224379911460490$
Of=-3.9302112862347631076737735681326661055 E-20 - 1.9637331365795475575582972470005782774 E-20*I

Result obtained by $a=1/2$ and $b=500000000.6466036686084991574606503056331$
Of=7.8080866907778165841320492097149156871 E-22 + 3.8208954121809938946047093993744356337 E-22*I

Result obtained by $a=1/2$ and $b=2000000000.3334382785951883748640438647746$
Of=-2.8008011262453436891793112209395157752 E-24 + 3.9200277187930290089145748451904772447 E-23*I

Result obtained by $a=1/2$ and $b=30384448732.3640552296259736345121804170722$ ($\backslash p 100$)
Of=1.583814110884789509819582339881791771493561334037305249397423543231884734053697782131863195969232870 E-26 - 2.483447501427731202218978136506730769108710696671302080370097573077748525669772787208866542518811663 E-26*I

In addition to what is described in this appendix, in the last command lines you can notice another difference, compared to the command lines in section (6.1), from which they derive.

In section (6.1) I highlighted how in every trace, pairs of vectors compete for the closest proximity to the origins, which follow one another until the last one. I proposed to use the decimal part of b/π , to establish which of the two vectors is closer to the origin.

The proposed verification was based on the decimal part of b/π , having 0.5 as reference. In the same section I highlighted that as the value of (b) increases and the closer the vectors are to the origins, plus the comparison of the orientations of two consecutive vectors approaches π radians, net of the multiples of 2π . By increasing the value of (b) it is evident that the oscillation of the two vectors, around the last origin, occurs with the two vectors alternately overtaking each other. The alternation of the two vectors to be the closest to the origin, corresponds to the overtaking.

In the command lines present in this appendix, I replaced the verification based on the decimal part of b/π , with the comparison of the orientations of the two vectors. With this modification I have remedied the uncertainty (when the decimal part is close to 0.5) of the calculation based on the decimal part of b/π .

I have already highlighted that the pseudo-clothoids, are always better formed as they get closer to the last origin and also as (b) increases. The same trend towards improvement, is noted in the correspondence of the overtaking between the two vectors, with the decimal part of b/π .

Here are three examples of how the correspondence between overtaking and the decimal part of b/π changes. There is overtaking between $b/\pi=2.46$ and 2.47 , between $b/\pi=10.49$ and 10.495 , between $b/\pi=100.499$ and 100.4999 .

In Fig. D04 I compare three different integer part of b/π , paired with twelve possible decimal parts. To concentrate the comparison in a small space, the vectors are not present but their midpoints. I associated a multiplier (M) to each value of b/π , of which I reported only two decimal places.

At the vertices of the triangles are: A blue circle to indicate the midpoint of the last vector, a brown circle to indicate the midpoint of the first vector, a fuchsia circle to indicate the point resulting from the PARI-GP zeta(s) function. The point (Of) is identified by the green broken line, remember that the horizontal part results from (B) and the vertical part from (H).

The value of (M) is such that the length of the segment corresponding to (B) is always the same. Given $a > 0$, the precision of the method presented in this appendix, improves as (b) increases. The choice of having (B) constant highlights that, the improvement is not only due to the shorter length of the two vectors in question.

The Fig. D04 show how the position of the last origin changes with respect to the positions of the two midpoints, but also serves to highlight that, as (b) increases the method becomes more precise, despite the reduction in length of the vectors having been neutralized.

I remember that the horizontal green segments, corresponding to (B), are parallel to the vectors closest to (Of). As in the previous images, the vertex shared by the two vectors, is located to the left of the two midpoints.

The following link is to a page published by Clay Mathematics Institute, in which are collected, in addition to the to the photos of the Riemann's manuscript, other documents including the transcription and translation.

<https://www.claymath.org/collections/riemanns-1859-manuscript/>

Links to some of my preprints.

Note: The links below do not correspond to any of the published revisions, they are special links which always refer to the latest revision.

This is the link that corresponds to this preprint.

<http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8026759>

This is the link to the Italian version of this preprint.

<http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8026728>

Anyone interested in the path of my research on the Riemann hypothesis, can find useful references in: Riemann zeta function. Riemann Hypothesis and the axis of symmetry.

<http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7117684>

This is the link to my latest (before 2026) preprint.

The Riemann hypothesis may be true twice.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17472974>

The following links correspond to some of my preprints, published on zenodo.org

I should improve the form (and maybe I'll try with a new preprint) of the one about the mechanism of prime numbers.

Primality test. My second contribution.

<http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6397327>

Twin primes. Where they can be found.

<http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5902559>

News on the mechanism of prime numbers.

<http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5844231>

Goldbach's conjecture. Because I think it's true.

<http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5707187>

How and Why to Use my Basic Scheme

to make Polygonal Spirals.

<http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5575215>

Dante Servi

Via Palmiro Togliatti, 14

Bressana Bottarone (PV) Italy

dante.servi@gmail.com